

**The application of contractual tools to the adjustment of fiscal regime
in renewable energy projects: within a framework of energy justice
centered on transactional justice**

Mostapha Maddahinasab

Institute for mining and energy law, Ruhr-University Bochum, Bochum, Germany

Mostapha.Maddahinasab@ruhr-uni-bochum.de

01.09.2023

Bochum, Germany

Acknowledgment

This research was sponsored by the Alexander von Humboldt Foundation under the Georg Forster postdoctoral fellowship program. As well as the German Academic Exchange Service (DAAD), with its program Bridge Scholarship Iran 2023. During this research, the author was a guest researcher at the Institute for Mining and Energy Law (IBE), Ruhr-University of Bochum, Germany. As well, Professor Dr. Christian Pielow's support as the IBE director is greatly appreciated.

The opinions expressed and arguments employed herein are not necessarily those of the institutions listed above.

To fix the grammar and enhance the language AI has been used to revise the text.

Dedicated to the unwavering love and endless support of my parents, who have been the brightest stars throughout my journey.

Embarking on my postdoctoral research journey was a dream I had nurtured for years. The goal was clear: delve into the realm of renewable energy development, merging the well-established legal and contractual tools from the petroleum sector with the vision of clean and sustainable energy solutions. It was a path I envisioned, one that would contribute to a brighter, more sustainable future.

The pivotal moment arrived on November 4, 2020, when I proudly received my PhD in Oil and Gas Law from the esteemed University of Tehran, Iran. This academic milestone was only the beginning of my journey toward a deeper exploration of renewable energy, as I had already secured acceptance into the prestigious Alexander von Humboldt Foundation postdoctoral fellowship program in Germany.

In February 2021, I arrived in Bochum, with a determined spirit and a passion for making a difference in the renewable energy landscape.

By June 2021, I had officially commenced my postdoctoral research, laying the foundation for what would become an exciting and fruitful exploration into the legal intricacies of renewable energy projects. The journey has already borne fruit, with one of my articles, "Joint Management Committee in Renewable Energy Projects," finding its way into the *Journal of Energy Policy Studies*. I am delighted to share that this article is readily available as open access, encouraging others to delve into its findings.

As I stand at this juncture, I am filled with gratitude for the opportunities that have come my way and the support that has fueled my journey thus far. Looking ahead, I am eager to continue this path, seeking the next fellowship or grant that will enable me to further advance the research that was ignited during my postdoctoral tenure. I am confident that this journey will lead to the creation of more papers and publications that will contribute to the ongoing dialogue surrounding renewable energy development.

I invite you to join me on this journey, as we collectively explore the potential of renewable energy and its pivotal role in shaping a sustainable and environmentally conscious future. Together, we can make a difference

Mostapha Maddahinasab (Ph.D.)

01. 09. 2023

Bochum, Germany

Table of contents

Contents

Abstract.....	7
Introduction	9
Hypothesis	11
Literature review.....	13
Methodology.....	18
1. Energy justice paradigm	22
1.1. Transactional energy justice	24
1.2. Epistemology	26
2. Renewable energy contracts	28
2.1. Power construction contracts.....	28
2.2. Electricity supply and sale contracts	31
2.2.1. Wholesale contracts.....	32
2.2.2. Spot contracts	35
2.2.3. Hedging contract.....	36
2.2.4. Feed-in tariff contracts.....	38
3. Adjustable fiscal regime	41
3.1. Fiscal regime of renewable energy projects	42
3.2. RE fiscal risks.....	45
3.2.1. Stranded costs	47
3.2.2. Stranded assets.....	51

3.2.3. Expenditures	53
3.2.4. Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE)	55
3.2.5. Marginal cost	57
3.2.6. Maximum competitive price in the market.....	60
3.3. R-Factor mechanism.....	62
3.3.1. Price-based R-factor	66
3.3.2. Risk/Performance-based R factor.....	68
4. Necessary contractual tools for dynamic fiscal regime adjustment	71
4.1. Joint management committee	71
4.1.1. JMC design for RE projects	75
4.1.2. Comparison with regulatory committees.....	81
4.2. Stabilization and renegotiation clauses	82
4.2.1. Stabilization Clauses in Renewable Energy Projects	82
4.2.2. Renegotiation clauses	86
Conclusion.....	89
References	92

Abstract

Clean and renewable energy sources are essential in combating environmental challenges, reducing greenhouse gas emissions, and ensuring a sustainable future. Technologies such as solar, wind, hydro, and geothermal power offer viable alternatives to fossil fuels, leading to cleaner energy and economic growth. Progress in achieving clean energy goals is evident, with renewables projected to make up 35% of global power generation by 2025. However, there is still a need for more renewable energy to address climate change, energy security, and affordability issues. Robust public policy support and incentive mechanisms like Feed-in Tariffs and Renewable Portfolio Standards have driven the advancement of renewable energy. However, the existing contractual framework lacks incentives for investors to take on higher risks.

To enhance the fiscal regime of renewable energy projects, the research proposes a contractual approach based on the R-factor mechanism. This approach aims to empower investors to shoulder greater risks, make larger investments, and receive equitable rewards, ensuring a sustainable and reliable energy future.

The research adopts a comprehensive methodology, drawing data from diverse secondary sources to establish a robust framework for informed decision-making in the energy sector. It is grounded in the theory of energy justice, with its own definition of energy justice centered on transactional justice. The methodology transcends specific legal systems, focusing on the holistic concept of law and its connection to energy justice. It uses a comparative approach, analyzing both the petroleum and renewable energy sectors to understand the complexities of contracts shaping fiscal regimes in renewable energy projects. The goal is to design a tailored R-factor mechanism to address these complexities. The research aims to provide valuable insights and recommendations to

advance clean energy within energy justice paradigm and promote sustainable and equitable energy practices.

The research concludes that The R-factor mechanism offers a dynamic, flexible, sustainable and quantifiable approach to ensure fairness and stability for investors and host states in renewable energy projects. By being compatible with the transactional energy justice framework, the R-factor promotes balance and enhances the energy market. Contractual clauses and tools, such as stabilization and renegotiation clauses and the joint management committee, support the functioning of the R-factor mechanism, facilitating risk-sharing and harmonizing different contracts within renewable energy projects.

Keywords: Renewable energy, Energy justice, Transactional justice, Fiscal regimes, Power purchase agreements, Feed-in tariff, R-factor, Rate of return, Joint management committee

Introduction

Clean and renewable energy sources play a pivotal role in addressing the pressing environmental challenges of our time. Their importance cannot be overstated, as they offer viable solutions to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, combat climate change, and safeguard the health of our planet. Clean energy sources, such as solar, wind, hydro, and geothermal power, provide an abundant and sustainable alternative to fossil fuels, which are major contributors to air pollution and global warming. By harnessing these renewable resources, we can significantly decrease our reliance on finite and polluting energy sources, leading to a cleaner and more sustainable future. Additionally, clean energy technologies promote economic growth and job creation, fostering innovation and investment in green industries. The transition to clean and renewable energy not only mitigates environmental risks but also enhances energy security, diversifying our energy mix and reducing geopolitical tensions associated with fossil fuel dependence. Embracing clean energy is a crucial step towards a greener, healthier, and more resilient planet for present and future generations.

The current state of achieving clean energy goals is showing promising progress, as evidenced by data collected from reputable organizations that track the development of renewable energy. According to the recent International Energy Agency's (IEA) Electricity Market Report 2023, The share of renewables in the global power generation mix is forecast to rise from 29% in 2022 to 35% in 2025. As renewables expand, the shares of coal- and gas-fired generation are set to fall. This is a significant increase compared to previous years and demonstrates the accelerating momentum towards cleaner energy alternatives. Furthermore, countries are actively setting ambitious targets and making considerable investments in renewable energy infrastructure. Several nations have already achieved or surpassed their renewable energy goals, while others are steadily

making progress towards their targets. Nonetheless, the report indicates a significant increase in energy demand after the Covid-19 restrictions. Furthermore, the invasion of Russia into Ukraine and the energy crisis have made renewable energy development not only a matter of sustainability and environment protection, but an emergency for energy security. According to the report, affordability of the energy is also a demanding issue, especially for developing countries.

Therefore, despite the increasing trends in clean energy, we still need a lot more renewable energy. Even if we assume that the current level of clean energy generation is sufficient to meet SDG standards, to tackle climate change and environmental issues, more affordable and ample clean energy is still needed to tackle energy security and affordability challenges.

The current advancement of Renewable Energy (RE) owes its progress to robust public policy support and incentive mechanisms, such as tax incentives and guarantee purchase programs like the Feed-in Tariff (FIT) and Renewable Portfolio Standards (RPS). However, for substantial investment to flow into the renewable energy sector, it is imperative to revamp the contractual framework governing these projects. Currently, the existing contract structures fail to incentivize investors to undertake higher risks. To establish risk-bearing contractual frameworks for RE projects, the fiscal regime within these contract settings must evolve and be strengthened. As larger RE projects entail greater capital requirements, they inherently involve amplified risks. However, with a well-defined contractual fiscal regime, heightened risks can correspondingly yield increased profits. Notwithstanding, the determination of fiscal regime provisions is typically embedded within sale contracts, such as Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs), or incorporated into FIT contracts when FIT mechanisms are employed. This poses

challenges in updating fiscal terms to facilitate investors' assumption of greater risks in exchange for a progressively rewarding and dependable fiscal regime.

To address this issue and enhance the fiscal regime of RE projects, I propose a contractual approach based on the R-factor mechanism through this research. The hypothesis and methodology aim to alleviate the existing constraints and enable investors to shoulder greater risks and allocate larger capital investments in these projects, while ensuring a reliable and equitable reward mechanism.

Hypothesis

As Renewable energy (RE) is usually based on decentralization it is challenging to apply an autonomous fiscal regime on these projects. Although many authors have suggested long-term contracts such as Power Purchase Agreements (PPA) as the solution¹, these projects still face inherent fiscal risks due to the limited flexibility of regulatory functions in adjusting rates, such as the price or Feed-in Tariff (FIT) rate. The regulatory frameworks often lack the necessary adaptability to set rates that align with the unique financial profiles of each RE project. As a result, there is a mismatch between the project's financial requirements and the rates established by the regulatory bodies. This discrepancy can create significant challenges and uncertainties for investors and project developers. Without the ability to tailor-fit rates to the specific characteristics and financial needs of each RE project, there is an increased likelihood of inadequate returns, reduced attractiveness for investment, and potential project viability concerns. It is crucial

¹ - V. Elistratov and I. Kudryasheva, 'Regimes, management and economics of energy complexes on the basis of renewable energy sources for autonomous power supply' (2019) 124 E3S Web Conf 04023

to address these fiscal risks by implementing mechanisms that offer greater flexibility and enable customized rate setting, ensuring a more harmonious alignment between the financial aspects of RE projects and the regulatory framework governing them.

The hypothesis of the research is to use R-factor mechanism and supporting contractual tools that can adjust the fiscal rates regularly. A basic R-factor formula is the ratio of accumulated receipts to accumulated expenditures;

$$R \text{ factor} = \frac{\textit{Accumulated receipts}}{\textit{Accumulated expenditures}}$$

The hypothesis behind utilizing the R-factor mechanism to address the aforementioned issue is grounded in the need for a tailored approach to adjusting the fiscal regime of renewable energy (RE) projects. The R-factor mechanism aims to provide a comprehensive and dynamic framework that takes into account the specific requirements and financial profiles of specific RE projects. By incorporating project-specific parameters, such as capital costs, maintenance and operational expenses, and revenue projections, the R-factor mechanism offers a more accurate assessment of the project's financial viability and risk profile.

The core idea is to establish a mechanism that dynamically adjusts the fiscal regime, particularly the rates or incentives, based on the R-factor, which represents the project's financial risk exposure. The mechanism thus provides measurements that allow decision-makers to adjust incentives or prices (or generally projects' return rates) based on the policies and strategies that are being applied. This customized approach ensures that the fiscal regime aligns with the unique characteristics and financial needs of each RE project, enhancing investor confidence, promoting project viability, and encouraging greater capital investment.

By implementing the R-factor mechanism, regulators can strike a balance between risk and reward, optimizing the fiscal regime to attract investment while safeguarding

financial sustainability. This approach recognizes that RE projects vary significantly in terms of technology, scale, location, and financing requirements. Therefore, a one-size-fits-all fiscal regime may not effectively address the diverse challenges and opportunities within the RE sector. The hypothesis posits that by tailoring the fiscal regime through the R-factor mechanism, regulatory bodies can provide a more equitable and efficient framework that supports the financial viability of RE projects, accelerates their deployment, and fosters a sustainable transition to clean energy.

Literature review

The concept of using project-specific mechanisms for adjusting the fiscal regime of renewable energy projects is an area of ongoing research and discussion among scholars and experts in the field. The aim is to address the limitations of traditional fixed-rate or incentive-based fiscal regimes, which may not adequately account for the diverse financial profiles and risk factors associated with different renewable energy projects.

Research on this topic explores the need for customized approaches to fiscal regimes and proposes mechanisms that consider project-specific parameters incorporating factors such as capital costs, operational expenses, revenue projections, and risk assessment, offers a promising avenue for tailoring the fiscal regime to the specific requirements of renewable energy projects.

A comprehensive review of the relevant literature pertaining to my research topic has revealed numerous publications highlighting the significance of long-term sale contracts, commonly referred to as Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs), in effectively managing fiscal and financial risks associated with renewable energy (RE) projects. These studies suggest that PPAs serve as a crucial mechanism for mitigating uncertainties and enhancing the bankability of RE projects. By establishing long-term agreements

between project developers and off-takers, typically utilities or corporate buyers, PPAs provide a stable revenue stream and predictable cash flows over an extended period.² Power purchase agreements govern a significant fraction of the transactions from independent renewable energy projects. As the costs of wind, solar and storage have plummeted in recent years and accelerated the growth of renewables towards decarbonization, the nature of wind and solar-based power purchase agreements is also evolving from traditional energy contract to power contract that supplies on-demand renewable electricity. As the landscape of PPAs is evolving to embrace real-time on-demand power sale contracts, decisions about optimal technology and storage mix, compliance with weather-dependent technologies, and accepting intermittent renewable energy levels must be carefully considered. Achieving truly Round-The-Clock (RTC) supply on a large scale is economically challenging. Contractual provisions should aim to address pricing and fiscal terms adjustments to ensure fairness for both parties.³

In addition to the significance of long-term sale contracts, previous literature also suggests the use of future contracts or hedging contracts as viable strategies for managing risks and financing renewable energy (RE) projects. Future contracts enable project developers to lock in a predetermined price for future energy sales, thereby shielding them from price fluctuations and market uncertainties. By hedging against volatile energy prices, future contracts provide a level of risk protection, enhancing the financial

² - Steffen Jahn, Johanna Horsch, Andreas Hundt, 'Power Purchase Agreements and Financing Renewables: An Interdependency' (2021) 27 *The Journal of Structured Finance* 35

³ - Sourabh Jain, 'Exploring structures of power purchase agreements towards supplying 24x7 variable renewable electricity' (2022) 244 *Energy* 122609

feasibility of RE projects.⁴ More specifically, Contracts for Difference (CfDs) offer valuable tools to guarantee a profitable fiscal regime for renewable energy projects while keeping renewable energy prices affordable.⁵ Nonetheless, as the minimum price is fixed, they do not encourage higher investments, technology updates, and project expansion through taking more risks. Therefore, as the total project costs must remain fixed due to the fixed minimum price, these projects cannot adapt to technological advancements or socio-economic and policy changes. This underscores the advantage of applying an R-factor mechanism in these contracts, indicating the novelty of the method proposed in my research.

Furthermore, hedging contracts offer an avenue for managing operational risks associated with RE projects. For instance, weather derivatives or hedging instruments can be employed to mitigate revenue fluctuations caused by weather variability, ensuring a stable income stream even in adverse weather conditions.⁶ This risk management approach provides valuable support to project developers and investors, improving the overall attractiveness of RE projects to potential financiers.⁷

⁴ - H. Tavafoghi and D. Teneketzis, 'Multidimensional Forward Contracts Under Uncertainty for Electricity Markets' (2017) 4 IEEE Transactions on Control of Network Systems 511

⁵ - Mats Kröger, Karsten Neuhoff and Jörn C Richstein, 'Contracts for difference support the expansion of renewable energy sources while reducing electricity price risks' (2022) 12 DIW Weekly Report 205

⁶ - S. Bhattacharya and others, 'Hedging strategies for risk reduction through weather derivatives in renewable energy markets' (2015 International Conference on Renewable Energy Research and Applications (ICRERA)) 1190

⁷ - M. Shamsi and P. Cuffe, 'Using Binary Prediction Markets as Hedging Instruments: Strategies for Renewable Generators' (2022) 13 IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy 1160

The literature highlights that the combination of long-term sale contracts, such as PPAs, and hedging contracts offers a robust risk management framework that addresses both short-term price volatility and long-term uncertainties. By employing a mix of these contractual arrangements, RE projects can secure reliable revenues and reduce exposure to financial risks.⁸ Nevertheless, these methods do not necessarily encourage project developers to take more risks and update the technology during the term of contract.

Furthermore, existing literature underscores the critical role of contract supply chain management and coordination in the contracts involved in every aspect of a renewable energy (RE) project from inception to completion.⁹ Studies highlight that successful RE projects depend on effective collaboration and coordination among various contract stakeholders, including technology providers, contractors, engineering firms, regulatory authorities, and financing institutions. The literature emphasizes that aligning contractual relationships throughout the supply chain is essential for optimizing project efficiency, risk mitigation, and cost management.¹⁰ contract supply chain management helps ensure timely procurement of equipment and services, reducing potential delays

⁸ - S. Hollmén, F. Levihn and G. Martinsson, 'When markets don't deliver : – bilateral hedging by means of PPAs in managing intertemporal price risks in power generation investments' (2022 18th International Conference on the European Energy Market (EEM))

⁹ - G Tomas M Hult, David J Ketchen Jr and Ernest L Nichols Jr, 'An examination of cultural competitiveness and order fulfillment cycle time within supply chains' (2002) 45 Academy of management Journal 577

¹⁰ - F. Ralston and others, 'Risk constrained contracting strategies of renewable portfolios' (2010 7th International Conference on the European Energy Market)

and project bottlenecks.¹¹ Coordinating contracts from the early planning stages to the operational phase enables seamless project execution and promotes a unified approach among different project participants. Moreover, effective contract supply chain management aids in clarifying responsibilities, risk-sharing mechanisms, and dispute resolution procedures, fostering a cooperative atmosphere that is conducive to successful project delivery.¹²

In general, the previous literature demonstrate a deep understanding of know-what, but they fall short in addressing know-how. In contrast, my research endeavors to articulate the know-how by presenting a distinctive methodology that applies the R-factor mechanism specifically tailored for renewable energy (RE) projects.

The utilization of the R-factor mechanism has been a common practice in upstream petroleum contracts, particularly in risk service contracts (RSCs) where it is applied to adjust the contractor's remuneration based on the fee per barrel of crude oil. Notably, this fiscal regime tool finds application in Iran's IPCs (Iranian Petroleum Contracts)¹³ and Iraq's RSCs or Ecuador's petroleum risk service contracts.¹⁴

¹¹ - Joel D Wisner and Keah Choon Tan, 'Supply chain management and its impact on purchasing' (2000) 36 *Journal of Supply Chain Management* 33

¹² - Fernando S Oliveira, Carlos Ruiz and Antonio J Conejo, 'Contract design and supply chain coordination in the electricity industry' (2013) 227 *European Journal of Operational Research* 527

¹³ - M Maddahinasab, 'Fiscal analysis of new Iranian petroleum contract called IPC from a legal and contractual perspective' (2017) 15 *Oil, Gas & Energy Law*

¹⁴ - Dongkun Luo and Xu Zhao, 'Modeling optimal oil production paths under risk service contracts' (2013) 10 *Petroleum Science* 596

In the extensive body of literature exploring the role of the R-factor in petroleum contracts and its impact on managing the contractor's rate of return, one of my articles stands out as a prominent contribution.¹⁵ In that article we studied the intricacies of the R-factor mechanism, shedding light on its effectiveness in aligning the interests of both parties and ensuring a fair and equitable remuneration structure. With a focus on optimizing the contractor's rate of return, the study presents valuable insights into the application and potential enhancements of the R-factor mechanism in the context of petroleum contracts.

Methodology

The research is grounded in a wealth of data collected from diverse secondary sources, including open-access findings from previous studies and library resources. Its practical objective is to establish a robust framework that transforms collected data into information to facilitate informed decision-making in the energy sector. As such, the research methodology primarily adopts evaluative, qualitative, and analytical approaches. The first step involves elucidating the conceptual underpinnings of my research, which centers on the theory of energy justice. In this context, I have put forth my own conceptualization of energy justice, serving as the foundational pillar upon which the theoretical framework of the research is built. Therefore, the first chapter delves into the energy justice paradigm and expounds on how it forms the bedrock for the research's theoretical development.

¹⁵ - SN Ebrahimi and M Maddahinasab, 'Controlling Contractor's Rate of Return (ROR) in Risk Service Contracts with R-Factor Mechanism' (2018) 16 Oil, Gas & Energy Law

As the research is not empirical,¹⁶ the methodology does not confine itself to a specific legal system. My research methodology perceives legal systems, regulations, and laws as manifestations of the law. Hence, while it may generally refer to some laws in various legal systems, it is not bound to a singular jurisdiction. Instead, it is grounded in the holistic noumenal concept of law, as interpreted through the lens of the energy justice concept, which acts as a conduit to the abstract and incomprehensible natural idea of the law. In other words, if we turn to Kant's distinction between the Noumenon (an object as it exists independently of our mind) and the phenomenon (our understanding and experience of an object), the noumenal law represents the elusive and indescribable dynamic nature of law, often referred to as natural law by jurists. On the other hand, the phenomenon of law encompasses the legal systems, legislation and regulations, legal norms, judicial decisions, and contracts (Positivistic law).¹⁷ While the prevalent legal methodology tends to analyze various legal phenomena to derive conclusions regarding another phenomenon, my methodology diverges from this approach. Instead, I strive to align my research findings with the ever-changing flow of the noumenal law. Consequently, I formulate hypotheses regarding the characteristics of the noumenal law within my research field and establish a framework that serves as a vessel for the noumenal law. Through this framework, I am able to investigate the specific legal

¹⁶ - The research is not going to test the hypothesis based on phenomenal primary data.

¹⁷ - Mostapha Maddahinasab, 'Legal and Philosophical Analysis of Ownership and sovereignty over hydrocarbon resources in concern with issues on internationally shared hydrocarbon reservoirs', University of Zurich 2018) p.9

phenomenon at hand in a manner that reflects the intrinsic nature of law.¹⁸ The framework will be like juncture that holds the epistemological relation between the source (noumenal law) and the research findings. In this research the framework is defined under the paradigm energy justice which will be discussed in a separate chapter.

Drawing upon the rich experiences of the petroleum industry, which has adeptly established complex and global markets with intricate international contractual arrangements, the research methodology adopts a comparative approach, analyzing both the petroleum sector and the renewable energy (RE) sector. By delving into the anatomy of contracts that shape the fiscal regime of RE projects, the research lays the groundwork for comprehending the key parameters and risks associated with these ventures—essential for designing a tailored R-factor mechanism. As the research unfolds, it explains relevant R-factor mechanisms and the necessary contractual institutions to support and sustain this mechanism.

In summary, the research employs a comprehensive and well-structured methodology, encompassing data analysis, theoretical formulation based on conceptual foundation, comparative analysis, and contractual elucidation, to unravel the complexities of fiscal regimes in RE projects. By embracing a holistic and inclusive approach, the research aims to provide valuable insights and actionable recommendations to advance the field of

¹⁸ - While there may be scholars who criticize my methodology, I firmly believe that it is the only path through which the field of law can transcend its existing boundaries. The conventional methodology, which entails examining legal phenomena solely to deduce another legal phenomenon, may address specific local issues in the present time. However, it falls short of pushing the frontiers of legal science and expanding our understanding of its nature.

energy justice and foster more sustainable and equitable energy practices.

1. Energy justice paradigm

Energy justice paradigm proposes an all-encompassing framework of values and objectives to ensure that energy policy is closely aligned with the public interest. Furthermore, its primary objective is to provide guidance for energy decision-making, enabling the (re)balancing of competing interests that govern the energy sector. In doing so, it seeks to foster a comprehensive and equitable energy landscape that serves the greater good.¹⁹

In recent times, numerous scholars have made substantial contributions to the burgeoning field of energy justice, resulting in its emergence as a flourishing interdisciplinary research domain. According to Jenkins and others, the growth in the literature on energy justice is due to its ‘appeal as a tangible, explanatory framework that is positioned as a conceptual, empirical and decision-making tool’.²⁰ Although since the 1980s, some fundamental aspects, cases, and remedies related to energy justice have been explored, these studies did not delve deeply into the term's contemporary understanding and the structured paradigm it embodies today. The current energy justice paradigm can trace its roots back to the environmental justice movement initiated in the USA by activists like Robert Bullard during the 1980s.²¹

¹⁹ - Laura Kaschny, 'Energy Justice and the Principles of Article 194 (1) TFEU Governing EU Energy Policy' (2023) *Transnational Environmental Law* 1

²⁰ - Kirsten EH Jenkins and others, 'Towards impactful energy justice research: transforming the power of academic engagement' (2020) *67 Energy Research & Social Science* 101510

²¹ - Joan Martinez-Alier and others, 'Is there a global environmental justice movement?' (2016) *43 The Journal of Peasant Studies* 731 p.9

Within the existing literature, two primary frameworks are prevalent for examining energy justice. The first framework centers on the philosophical conceptualization of justice and derives a set of principles intended for policy application, thereby aligning the energy sector with justice.²² Although it provides a good conceptual framework, it is worth considering that the notion of justice is not rigid but rather dynamic, varying across different locations and evolving over time. As a result, this particular perspective may lack practical efficacy due to its fixed nature and inability to account for contextual variations.²³ In the other framework, The focus is on a functional theoretical framework. It is basically known on three tenets:

1. distributive justice: concerned with the fair distribution of benefits and burdens across society. In the context of energy justice, it focuses on ensuring that everyone has access to affordable, reliable, and clean energy, regardless of their income, race, or location.
2. Procedural justice: concerned with ensuring that decision-making processes are fair and transparent. In the context of energy justice, it focuses on ensuring that communities are involved in decisions related to energy infrastructure and that their voices are heard.
3. Recognition justice: concerned with acknowledging and addressing the historical and cultural injustices that have affected certain communities.

²² - Benjamin K Sovacool and Michael H Dworkin, 'Energy justice: Conceptual insights and practical applications' (2015) 142 *Applied Energy* 435

²³ - Kaschny, 'Energy Justice and the Principles of Article 194 (1) TFEU Governing EU Energy Policy' and also Jenkins and others, 'Towards impactful energy justice research: transforming the power of academic engagement'

In the context of energy justice, it focuses on ensuring that the rights and interests of indigenous peoples, minorities, and other marginalized groups are respected and upheld.²⁴

Hazrati and Heffron have added restorative justice to these tenets, so that making it more practical. It is concerned with repairing the harm that has been done to individuals and communities. In the context of energy justice, it focuses on compensating those who have been adversely affected by energy production or consumption, and working to restore damaged ecosystems and communities.²⁵

1.1. Transactional energy justice

As previously mentioned, my research methodology is deeply rooted in adapting to the fluid nature of the noumenon of law. Consequently, the energy justice framework I apply must embody qualities that align with this dynamic essence. To this end, I introduce a new tenet to the existing paradigm of energy justice, termed "Transactional Energy Justice." This concept refers to the dynamic state of fairness achieved through active and purposeful cooperation among stakeholders, culminating in a win-win solution for all parties involved. The concept of transactional justice is not in opposition to the concept of "distributional justice" but rather the former complements the latter. In fact, transactional justice is the missing linchpin for the energy justice framework to work.

²⁴ - Kirsten Jenkins and others, 'Energy justice: A conceptual review' (2016) 11 Energy Research & Social Science 174. Also see Raphael J Heffron and Darren McCauley, 'The concept of energy justice across the disciplines' (2017) 105 Energy Policy 658

²⁵ - Mohammad Hazrati and Raphael J Heffron, 'Conceptualising restorative justice in the energy transition: changing the perspectives of fossil fuels' (2021) 78 Energy research & social science 102115

If the energy justice framework is to serve as an effective vessel for the noumenon of law, the framework must possess certain crucial qualities:

1. **Inclusiveness:** The framework must bring together all stakeholders, fostering collaboration and participation from everyone involved. This inclusivity is essential to achieve a fair balance in the energy trilemma—addressing affordability, energy security, and environment protection.
2. **Dynamism:** Recognizing that the balance within the energy trilemma is not static, the framework should establish fairness across all aspects of the trilemma, adapting to varying contexts and changing circumstances. Prioritizing different elements may be necessary based on different countries and times.
3. **Flexibility:** To maintain the dynamic balance in the energy trilemma, the framework must be flexible, enabling stakeholders, mechanisms, institutions, and policies within the energy sector to adapt swiftly and continuously towards a fair and dynamic equilibrium. Such adaptation must align with the evolving concept of fairness and justice, without relying solely on legislations or regulatory decisions that always lag behind such social, cultural, economic and environmental developments.
4. **Sustainability:** Long-term perspectives must underpin the mechanisms within the energy justice framework to reduce the need for constant governmental interventions and amendments. Sustainable procedures ensure that effective practices endure to benefit others in different countries and future periods.
5. **Quantification:** Achieving a fair (win-win) solution necessitates the application of quantitative methods. Measurement, comparison, and

benchmarking based on quantitative tools are crucial to ensure stakeholders and communities appreciate the fairness within the framework.

6. Integration into the international energy sector: The energy justice framework must be universally applicable in the international arena. This objective is achievable when the aforementioned qualities are embedded in the framework. Countries with diverse energy agendas will be more receptive to mechanisms that exhibit inclusivity, dynamism, flexibility, sustainability, and measurability.

By grounding the framework on the concept of transactional energy justice, it becomes possible to embody these essential qualities. In energy transactions, stakeholders should convene and engage in fair bargaining, leading to a balanced and flexible outcome. Long-term structures automatically sustain this equilibrium, enabling collaboration even amid competition. Moreover, incorporating economic factors and criteria renders the framework quantifiable, facilitating its integration into the international energy sector. Ultimately, this holistic approach enhances harmony and equitable growth, fostering fair and sustainable energy usage on a global scale.

1.2. Epistemology

The energy justice framework, rooted in transactional justice, lays the foundation for this research, delineating the logical discourse that drives the investigation towards finding solutions aligning with the criteria elucidated in the preceding section. Thus, the research endeavors to examine its hypothesis within this framework, focusing on the potential and efficacy of applying the R-factor mechanism and complementary contractual mechanisms. The primary objective is to determine if these mechanisms can engender a

fair bargaining structure that results in a win-win solution while maintaining sustainability amidst market fluctuations, regulatory dynamics, and other external factors impacting the energy sector. Additionally, the research aims to assess the feasibility of these methods for incorporation into international energy practices. Embracing this venue of inquiry shapes the epistemological trajectory of the research, driving towards achieving solutions that harmoniously fit within the energy justice framework with the aforementioned characteristics.

2. Renewable energy contracts

In the realm of the Renewable Energy (RE) and electricity sector, a plethora of contract names come into play, making it appear perplexing to discern the specific contract types governing the intricate relations among companies involved in an electricity or RE project, from inception to completion. Broadly speaking, these contracts can be classified into two main categories:

1. **Construction Contracts:** These contracts pertain to the initial phase of the electricity project, focusing on the construction and development of the necessary infrastructure, equipment, and facilities. Construction contracts lay the groundwork for the project, encompassing various elements such as engineering, procurement, construction, and commissioning.
2. **Supply and Sale Contracts:** Once the electricity project is operational, supply and sale contracts come into play, governing the agreements between suppliers and utilities. These contracts outline the terms and conditions for the supply and sale of electricity, ensuring a seamless and reliable flow of power to end-users.

With this distinction, the complex web of contracts in the electricity sector becomes more comprehensible, delineating the roles and responsibilities of each party involved in the project's lifecycle.

2.1. Power construction contracts

Power construction contracts govern the development of power plants or power grids, and they typically fall into two main prototypes: 1- Private-Public Participation (PPP) Contracts: PPP contracts exhibit versatility, ranging from concessions to Joint Ventures (JVs) and encompassing service contracts. These contracts are well-suited for projects

with higher risks and uncertainties. Public participation in PPP contracts helps mitigate risks by providing support and resources during project execution. PPP contracts often involve the contractor in the operation and management of the power plant or grid.²⁶ 2-Turnkey Contracts: Turnkey contracts are pure service contracts. This contract format are more fitting for projects with fewer uncertainties. That is why these contracts are also known as “lump sum contracts”. They are suitable for less complex projects where the project owner can handle the operation of the power plant independently, without the need for extensive contractor involvement in this aspect.²⁷

Within these contract types, various variations and models exist. One prominent example of a PPP contract is the Build-Operate and Transfer (BOT) contract, where the private sector undertakes the construction and operation of an infrastructure project for a specific concession period before transferring it to public authorities. Governments often grant concessions to motivate private investors to invest in capital-intensive and risky infrastructure projects like power plants and grids. Although monopolistic rights were previously granted to concession holders, most legal systems now embrace free and competitive market rules. BOT contracts provide temporary control and cash flow rights to concession holders, enabling them to recover their investment costs and achieve expected profits based on an open or limited Rate of Return (ROR).²⁸ Governments can

²⁶ - Meghdad Attarzadeh and others, 'Options-based negotiation management of PPP–BOT infrastructure projects' (2017) 35 Construction management and economics 676

²⁷ - Jonathan Hosie, 'Turnkey contracting under the FIDIC Silver Book: What do owners want? What do they get?' (2007) London, UK

²⁸ - Emmanuelle Auriol and Pierre M Picard, 'A theory of BOT concession contracts' (2013) 89 Journal of economic behavior & organization 187, pp. 187-188

incentivize private sector investment by offering longer concession periods, higher ROR, or guaranteed levels of ROR. Simultaneously, governments can control concession holders' profits and protect against pitfalls through methods like taxation or revenue-sharing.²⁹

Turnkey contracts, on the other hand, present fixed obligations, making it easier for the contractor to assess the CAPEX (capital expenditure) and non-CAPEX costs required for the project. The Engineering, Procurement, and Construction (EPC) contract is a prototype format of turnkey contracts, wherein the contractor manages the engineering, design, procurement of materials, and construction of the project.³⁰ The contractor guarantees the completion date, cost ceiling, and project quality and performance. EPC contracts are commonly used for infrastructure projects like transportation, power plants, and petrochemical facilities. The contractor bears economic risks related to price escalation (e.g., equipment costs) and the risk of project delays. In return, the contractor receives a fixed remuneration fee plus cost recovery, simplifying the contract's fiscal regime.³¹

²⁹ - Sadegh Abdi and Mohamad Amin Salarian, 'Examining the Contractual Methods and Patterns of Financing Infrastructure Projects with Emphasis on Build, Operation, Transfer Contracts' (2022) 7 International Journal of Finance & Managerial Accounting 115

³⁰ - Yong Qiang Chen and others, 'Analysis of project delivery systems in Chinese construction industry with data envelopment analysis (DEA)' (2010) Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management 598, p. 599

³¹ - P Lee, PTI Lam and Wai Ling Lee, 'Risks in energy performance contracting (EPC) projects' (2015) 92 Energy and Buildings 116 p.125

However, as projects become more complex, the EPC contract may evolve into other formats to accommodate additional responsibilities and risks. For instance, an EPCF contract involves the contractor handling project financing³², while EPCOM contracts require the contractor to operate and maintain the project.³³ These complex projects demand more flexible contractual fiscal regimes, often allowing the contractor to recover costs and profits from project revenues. Larger projects may involve subcontractors for various phases or components, necessitating a holistic approach to efficiently manage risks and operations throughout the project's lifecycle.

The primary risk associated with the construction contract fiscal regime is revenue instability.³⁴ As a result, the viability and profitability of construction contracts are determined by the fiscal regime outlined in electricity sale contracts.

2.2. Electricity supply and sale contracts

Electricity supply and sale contracts exhibit a diverse array, influenced by factors like contract duration, electricity volume, market pricing mechanisms, and risk management provisions within the fiscal framework. When categorizing these contracts within the electricity market, three primary types emerge; 1- wholesale contracts (also known as

³² - Mahsa Bahadoran-Baghbaderani and Ahmad Mohamadi, 'Legal study of foreign investment restrictions and project financing through the implementation of engineering, procurement, construction, and finance (EPCF) contracts' (2021) 27 Journal encyclopedia of economic law 29

³³ - Ioannis E Tsolas, 'Benchmarking engineering, procurement and construction (EPC) power plant projects by means of series two-stage DEA' (2020) 1 electricity 1

³⁴ - Attarzadeh and others, 'Options-based negotiation management of PPP–BOT infrastructure projects'

bilateral contracts or power purchase agreements), 2-spot contracts, 3-hedging contracts, 4-Feed-in Tariff contract (FIT)

2.2.1. Wholesale contracts

Contracts in the wholesale market are known as bilateral contracts. In these contracts, the power generators on one side are the sellers and the utilities on the other side are the buyers.³⁵ Regarding renewable energy, the most important format of bilateral contract is Power Purchase Agreement (PPA). In such an agreement, the output of a power plant (entirely or partially) is sold for the long term (one year or more) to a utility for a fixed or variable price. Power purchase agreements (PPAs) are large, long-term, and relatively infrequent transactions with large sums and considerable risks.³⁶ There is risk over prices of both inputs and outputs. A limited number of potential traders and low liquidity are common problems. Traditional PPAs are not suited to reacting to changing information about costs, demand, and prices. PPAs are categorized into five types; 1- fixed charge payment, 2- variable charge payment, 3- incentive payment, 4- transfer price. A fixed rate of return (fixed charge payment) is more common in the electricity sector.³⁷ Certain Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs) offer variable pricing. This entails adjusting the contract price based on the prevailing market rates for each transaction during the

³⁵ - Collin Cain, Jonathan Lesser and Bates White, *A common sense guide to wholesale electric markets*, 2007) p.11

³⁶ - F Huneke and others, 'Power purchase agreements: financial model for renewable energies' (2018) Energy Brainpool White Paper , p.2

³⁷ - Glenn Jenkins and Henry Lim, *An integrated analysis of a power purchase agreement*, 1999) 698

contract's term. However, while this strategy offers adaptability, it also exposes both parties to market price risks. This aspect becomes a deterrent for renewable energy developers, as they face the possibility of insufficient cost recovery and profitability if market prices fall too low.³⁸

Given the paramount importance of renewable energy in many jurisdictions, where policies and strategies are designed to incentivize investments in clean energy, a new format of PPA has emerged—the Contract for Difference (CfD). This innovative arrangement seeks to address the shortcomings of variable pricing (or sliding feed-in premiums) and provides a viable solution for renewable energy projects. A CfD guarantees a fixed price for the renewable energy generated by a specific project over a predetermined period. This price is often higher than the prevailing market price for electricity to make renewable energy projects financially viable and attractive to investors. The payments to the renewable energy producers are usually the difference between the guaranteed CfD price and the actual market price of electricity. If the market price is higher than the CfD price, the energy producer pays the difference back to the energy regulator or utility. On the other hand, if the market price is lower, the energy producer receives the difference from the regulator or utility, ensuring they receive a stable income and consumers pay affordable prices.³⁹ One of the challenges associated with CfDs lies in their potential disincentive for developers to make further investments

³⁸ - RB Shrestha and Stephen Ogunlan, 'Comparative study of Power Purchase Agreements in the Nepalese environment' (2006) 11 Journal of Financial Management of Property and Construction 133 p.138

³⁹ - Nils May, Karsten Neuhoff and Jörn C Richstein, 'Affordable electricity supply via contracts for difference for renewable energy' (2018) 8 DIW Weekly Report 251 p.255

and technological updates to their projects during the contract period. This is due to the cumulative cost increase that occurs when enhancing the project, potentially making the fixed minimum guaranteed price inadequate. Consequently, a dynamic adjustment mechanism, such as the R-factor, becomes essential to address this issue effectively.

Traditional Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs) have overlooked the importance of accounting for hourly or sub-hourly generation details. In the past, due to the must-run status of renewable energy sources, customers were obliged to purchase the energy whenever it was produced, subject to certain yearly limits. However, as storage costs have decreased, the landscape of PPAs has evolved to embrace real-time on-demand power sale contracts. For instance, novel concepts like hybrid systems combining wind and solar, Variable Renewable Energy (VRE) with a few hours of storage, or round-the-clock (RTC) Renewable Energy supply contracts have gained significant traction. The emergence of 24/7 arrangements reflects the dispatchable nature of storage-based Renewable Energy systems, where the energy generator can fulfill both annual energy delivery commitments and hourly power obligations. This shift in PPA dynamics represents a move away from fixed annual quantities to more flexible and responsive arrangements that cater to real-time energy needs. The introduction of such ambitious contractual structures in newer types of Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs) creates challenges for buyers and sellers. Decisions about optimal technology and storage mix, compliance with weather-dependent technologies, and accepting intermittent renewable energy levels must be carefully considered. Achieving truly Round-The-Clock (RTC)

supply on a large scale remains economically challenging. Contractual provisions should aim to address pricing and fiscal terms adjustments to ensure fairness for both parties.⁴⁰

Given the strategies aimed at promoting greater renewable energy usage, alternative fiscal regimes that incentivize risk-taking based on real-time market conditions may be more suitable. Consequently, effectively managing risks in these agreements becomes crucial. This research delves into the R-factor mechanism to explore its potential application in addressing these challenges.

2.2.2. *Spot contracts*

Occasionally, power generators encounter operational challenges in their plants, particularly in the case of renewable energy where weather conditions may hinder the scheduled supply of electricity to utilities under the Power Purchase Agreement (PPA). When such situations arise, they may need to acquire the remaining scheduled quantity from the spot market. Additionally, there are instances when a surge in energy demand requires utilities to purchase from the spot market to meet the deficit. In both scenarios, the spot market plays a crucial role in balancing supply and demand in real-time. As this market is sensitive to instantaneous events affecting energy availability and requirements, its volatility can be relatively high. To mitigate the risks associated with such fluctuating prices, hedging contracts are employed as effective risk control tools.⁴¹

⁴⁰ - Jain, 'Exploring structures of power purchase agreements towards supplying 24x7 variable renewable electricity'

⁴¹ - Shi-Jie Deng and Shmuel S Oren, 'Electricity derivatives and risk management' (2006) 31 Energy 940, p. 941

2.2.3. Hedging contract

Uncertainty in demand is a common feature of commodity markets, which is mostly managed through using stored goods. As storage is challenging in the electricity market, the price in the electricity market is very volatile.⁴² Therefore, the hedging contracts are applied to manage the risk.

According to Zhang and Wang, 'hedging is buying a derivative to offset the risk of a cash position, which is the amount of energy owned'. Hedging contracts are financial instruments (derivatives) that do not represent ownership rights in energy but rather derive their value from the value of an underlying commodity or another asset.⁴³

In terms of how they optimize risk management for utilities, there are different types of hedge contracts. The purpose of using hedging contracts is to distribute the volatile price risk in the spot market between the participants of the market.⁴⁴

The hedging contracts can be categorised under four main types; 1- forward contracts, 2- future contracts, 3- options, 4- swaps.⁴⁵

A forward contract is a contract that obligates the holders to buy or sell an asset for a predetermined delivery price at a predetermined future time. Under a forward contract, the sum of the contract is paid at the maturity (delivery date) of the contract.

⁴² - Raphaël Homayoun Boroumand and others, 'Hedging strategies in energy markets: The case of electricity retailers' (2015) 51 Energy Economics 503, p. 503

⁴³ - Qin Zhang and Xifan Wang, 'Hedge contract characterization and risk-constrained electricity procurement' (2009) 24 IEEE Transactions on Power Systems 1547, p. 1547

⁴⁴ - Min Liu, Felix F Wu and Yixin Ni, *A survey on risk management in electricity markets* (IEEE 2006)

⁴⁵ - Deng and Oren, 'Electricity derivatives and risk management', p. 942

Future contracts are similar to forwarding contracts as they also obligate the two sides of the contract to sell or buy electricity at certain rates in the future. Nonetheless, there are differences between forward and futures contracts. A future contract is under regulations from the mandated authorities while forward contracts have no exchange regulations. Being based on exchange regulations a future contract has more liquidity, which means the contract holder can trade it by employing large contract sizes, and not worry about meeting someone on the other side of the trade. In a forward contract, on the other hand, parties privately determine the terms of the contract. An exchange is, therefore, not required for them to execute the transaction. Moreover, the exchange regulations make future contracts more price transparent with a standardized frame. That means with a future contract, one can look at historical trends of the market and identify trading opportunities. Under a forward contract, though the terms are uniquely agreed upon.⁴⁶

Option contracts refer to agreements that gives the buyer of electricity the right to buy (call option) or to sell (put option) the electricity at a predetermined price (the strike price) over a specified period.⁴⁷

A swap contract is a contractual frame for exchanging a series of cash flows generated by underlying assets between two participants in the electricity market. Swaps are created in part to give price certainty at a cost that is lower than the cost of options.⁴⁸ Under a swap contract, no commodity is actually transferred between the parties to the contract. Like forward contracts, swaps are also a form of on the counter (OTC) derivative, thus they

⁴⁶ - Liu, Wu and Ni, *A survey on risk management in electricity markets*

⁴⁷ - *ibid*

⁴⁸ - The Contract for Difference (CFD) can also be viewed as a hedging swap arrangement.

are not in a centralized, standardized trading structure.

2.2.4. Feed-in tariff contracts

The electricity market presents inherent complexities and risks, primarily due to the nature of the commodity, making storage challenging and transmission constrained by physical and reliability limitations.⁴⁹ Furthermore, Despite technological advancements leading to a decreasing Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) in renewable sources compared to conventional ones, large-scale renewable energy projects face significant upfront capital requirements and encounter grid integration issues due to the intermittent nature of renewable sources. Unlike conventional energy, renewable energy production levels fluctuate. Consequently, government support becomes essential for managing fiscal and financial risks necessary for fostering the advancement of clean energy sources, particularly during the initial phases of their development.⁵⁰

Feed-in tariff (FIT), in general, is a public policy to promote renewable electricity production. Perhaps it is the most effective and popular public policy instrument that policymakers in different countries have come up with. According to the renewables 2019

⁴⁹ - Min Liu and Felix F Wu, 'Risk management in a competitive electricity market' (2007) 29 International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems 690, p.690

⁵⁰ - Maria Teresa García-Alvarez and Rosa María Mariz-Pérez, 'Analysis of the success of feed-in tariff for renewable energy promotion mechanism in the EU: lessons from Germany and Spain' (2012) 65 Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences 52, p. 52

Global Status Report (REN21 2019), more than one hundred countries in 2018 applied the FIT mechanism to develop renewable energies.⁵¹

Under the FIT mechanism, the renewable energy producers are entitled to sell all their production in the electricity network.⁵² FIT contracts are held between governmental regulator (or public/governmental utility companies) and the renewable energy producers guaranteeing the purchase of the produced electricity. In general, two FIT schemes are common in different countries; 1- Fixed-price FIT (FFIT), which sets a fixed price for every unit of produced electricity. 2- Premium based FIT (PFIT), which pays a premium on top of the market price.

FFIT transfers price risk from producers to consumers helping the renewable energy sector to have high and stable growth (especially small producers like households). Nonetheless, PFIT is better for matching the production with the marginal costs of the production and the costs of balancing intermittent electricity production may be lower with PFIT.⁵³ Therefore, the PFIT scheme is more suitable for big renewable energy projects. Furthermore, since the PFIT scheme is tied to the market price, these kinds of FIT contracts play an important role in the entire sector, enhancing the counter

⁵¹ - Luciana Barbosa and others, 'Feed-in tariff contract schemes and regulatory uncertainty' (2020) 287 *European Journal of Operational Research* 331, p.331

⁵² - García-Alvarez and Mariz-Pérez, 'Analysis of the success of feed-in tariff for renewable energy promotion mechanism in the EU: lessons from Germany and Spain', p.53

⁵³ - Johannes Schmidt and others, 'Where the wind blows: Assessing the effect of fixed and premium based feed-in tariffs on the spatial diversification of wind turbines' (2013) 40 *Energy Economics* 269, pp. 269-270

effects between the different participants, and thus intensifying the necessity of constant coordination among them.⁵⁴

⁵⁴ - Barbosa and others, 'Feed-in tariff contract schemes and regulatory uncertainty', p.332

3. Adjustable fiscal regime

The R-factor concept has been long acknowledged as a valuable tool in shaping and adjusting contractual fiscal regimes.⁵⁵ Traditionally, it has thrived within the realm of upstream petroleum contracts, effectively balancing the interests of resource developers and host governments.⁵⁶ However, with the ongoing global shift towards renewable energy sources, there arises a pressing need to explore innovative approaches that can adapt fiscal regimes to the distinct characteristics of renewable energy projects. In this chapter, I aim to investigate the application of the R-factor concept in fine-tuning fiscal regimes for renewable energy projects, offering fresh insights into contract design and economic incentives within this rapidly evolving sector, with the energy justice perspective.

In this chapter, I will begin by providing essential definitions and highlighting the crucial attributes of fiscal regimes in renewable energy projects. Building on this foundation, I will explore the key factors and parameters that hold significance in designing effective fiscal regimes for such projects. Subsequently, I will present my recommendations for enhancing the fiscal regime in renewable energy projects, aligning it more efficiently with the actual output and risks involved. A prominent concern is that the incentives set by regulatory bodies lack objectivity, often leading to inadequacy or excessiveness in their application to diverse projects. Hence, by establishing a well-calibrated fiscal regime, we can ensure that the incentives strike the right balance, ensuring an appropriate ROR, motivating investment while fostering healthy competition

⁵⁵ - Ebrahimi and Maddahinasab, 'Controlling Contractor's Rate of Return (ROR) in Risk Service Contracts with R-Factor Mechanism'

⁵⁶ - *ibid*

with conventional sources of energy in the market. This equilibrium is crucial for nurturing a functional and thriving market for renewable energy, ultimately contributing to a sustainable and just energy transition.

3.1. Fiscal regime of renewable energy projects

Generally fiscal regime refers to any provisions that organize sharing of economic rents between the government and the investor (here a developer that produces RE).⁵⁷ there are two settings of fiscal regimes governing an energy production project: regulatory fiscal regime and contractual fiscal regime.⁵⁸ In this section I define and describe the characteristics and functions of each one building up toward articulation of the fiscal regime and its risks in RE projects.

A regulatory fiscal regime involves the imposition of taxes, fees, and other charges on companies that extract natural resources. Under this regime, the government sets the fiscal terms, which are designed to regulate the project in a particular area.

In a regulatory fiscal regime, the government typically sets the tax rates, royalty rates, and other charges that companies must pay in exchange for the right to extract natural resources or producing certain sources of energy. The government may also establish regulations and guidelines that govern the process, such as environmental protection requirements and safety standards or requirements of spatial planning laws.

⁵⁷ - Daniel Johnston, *International Petroleum Fiscal Systems-PSCs* (PennWell Publishing Company 1994) 5

⁵⁸ - Carole Nakhle, '4 Petroleum fiscal regimes: evolution and challenges' in Philip Daniel, Michael Keen and Charles McPherson (eds), *The taxation of petroleum and minerals* (Routledge 2010) 93

One of the main objectives of a regulatory fiscal regime is to ensure that the project is carried out in a responsible and sustainable manner. By imposing fiscal regulations and taxes, the government can encourage companies to adopt best practices and to minimize their impact on the environment.⁵⁹

Examples of regulatory fiscal regimes include the Norwegian tax regime for the petroleum industry and the Brazilian mining regulatory regime. These regimes have been established to ensure that companies extract natural resources in a sustainable and responsible manner, while also ensuring that the government receives a fair share of the economic benefits.⁶⁰

While it is common in other natural resources projects that under the regulatory fiscal regime, the investors pay rents to the governments, for RE projects, however, this is different since the governments either exempt the investors or pay them rents under the regulatory fiscal regime. This characteristic manifests itself under different policy frameworks, such as feed-in tariffs in Germany or tax reduction in the Netherlands and regional tax exemption in Italy and Spain.⁶¹

⁵⁹ - Sanford E Gaines and Asbjorn Eriksson, *Taxation for environmental protection: A multinational legal study* (Greenwood Publishing Group 1991) 6

⁶⁰ - Diderik Lund, 'State participation and taxation in Norwegian petroleum: Lessons for others?' (2014) 3 *Energy Strategy Reviews* 49 p.52 and Philip Andrews-Speed, 'Fiscal systems for mining - the case of Brazil' (1998) 13 *Minerals & Energy - Raw Materials Report* 13

⁶¹ - Robert Wand and Florian Leuthold, 'Feed-in tariffs for photovoltaics: Learning by doing in Germany?' (2011) 88 *Applied Energy* 4387, Kees W. Kwant, 'Renewable energy in The Netherlands: policy and instruments' (2003) 24 *Biomass and Bioenergy* 265 p.266, José M. Cansino and others, 'Tax incentives to promote green electricity: An overview of EU-27 countries' (2010) 38 *Energy Policy* 6000

On the other hand, contractual fiscal regime is a type of agreement between a governmental organ (in electricity sector, the regulator organ, or related utilities) and a company that outlines the economic rents that the company must pay or receive in exchange for the contractual right/obligation to extract natural resources in a particular area. Under this regime, the parties to a contract negotiate the terms of the agreement, which can include tax rates, the method of calculating royalties, and other financial obligations. The terms of the contract are typically designed to ensure that both the government and the company benefit from the resource extraction.⁶²

Contractual fiscal regime provides more flexibility in determining the financial obligations of the company. This can be advantageous for both the government and the company, as it allows them to tailor the agreement to their specific needs and circumstances.⁶³

As each RE project is based on different contract frames, from building a RE power plant to selling the produced energy, the contractual fiscal regime for these projects are scattered and cannot be determined in a single contract frame. For example, some contractual fiscal provisions are presented with construction contracts (such as BOTs, EPCs) and some are presented in sale contracts such as PPAs. Unless the parties in each contract setting are the same otherwise managing the fiscal/financial risks of the project will be difficult. If we assume that the constructor/operator has built the RE facilities for the public company responsible for providing energy for the host country, or a private utility that after the start of the operation of the project is the buyer of the produced energy,

⁶² - Johnston, *International Petroleum Fiscal Systems-PSCs*

⁶³ - Carlo Cottarelli, 'Fiscal regimes for extractive industries: Design and implementation' (2012)

International Monetary Fund 67 p.15

then the contractual and fiscal terms of the different phases of the project can be linked together, otherwise, that will be difficult requiring other strong risk management tools such as a R-factor mechanism an inclusive JMC in the project or other helpful contractual clauses such as elaborated renegotiation and stabilization clauses. In the research these mechanism are discussed to provide an integrated fiscal regime for RE projects. In the next sections the main fiscal/financial risks and other related RE parameters will be discussed, in order to design the R-factor mechanism tailored to RE projects.

3.2. RE fiscal risks

Renewable energy projects have various fiscal risks that need to be considered before investing in such projects. Some of the key fiscal risks associated with renewable energy projects are:

- **Cost overruns:** huge RE projects are often capital-intensive, which means there is a risk of cost overruns due to unexpected delays, regulatory hurdles, or other unforeseen circumstances. Cost overruns are more common in hydroelectric dams and nuclear energy, and less common in solar or wind energy. Nevertheless, if wind and solar energy projects are built in huge and complex scale, they can also be prone to cost overruns.⁶⁴
- **Fluctuations in Revenue:** RE projects generate revenue through the sale of energy. However, revenue streams may be affected by changes in the level of energy

⁶⁴ - Benjamin K. Sovacool, Alex Gilbert and Daniel Nugent, 'An international comparative assessment of construction cost overruns for electricity infrastructure' (2014) 3 Energy Research & Social Science 152

generation (due to weather conditions for instance), energy prices, supply and demand dynamics, and regulatory changes.⁶⁵

- **Policy and Regulatory Risks:** Governments and regulatory bodies may change policies or regulations that can impact the profitability of renewable energy projects. Changes in tariffs, subsidies, tax incentives, or other regulations can affect the viability of the project.⁶⁶
- **Technology Risks:** Renewable energy technologies are still evolving, and there is a risk that a new technology could emerge that is more efficient or cheaper, making the existing technology obsolete. Additionally, there is a risk of technology failure, which can result in costly repairs or downtime. Accurate technology assessment is the key to manage the risk.⁶⁷
- **Counterparty Risks:** Renewable energy projects often require long-term contracts with suppliers, contractors, and off-takers. However, there is a risk that a counterparty may not fulfil their obligations, resulting in financial losses.⁶⁸

⁶⁵ - Niels I. Meyer, 'European schemes for promoting renewables in liberalised markets' (2003) 31 Energy Policy 665 p.669

⁶⁶ - Nadine Gatzert and Thomas Kosub, 'Determinants of policy risks of renewable energy investments' (2017) 11 International journal of energy sector management 28

⁶⁷ - Florian Egli, Bjarne Steffen and Tobias S Schmidt, 'A dynamic analysis of financing conditions for renewable energy technologies' (2018) 3 Nature Energy 1084

⁶⁸ - Nadine Gatzert and Thomas Kosub, 'Risks and risk management of renewable energy projects: The case of onshore and offshore wind parks' (2016) 60 Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews 982 p.992

- **Financing Risks:** Renewable energy projects are often financed through debt, which can result in interest rate risks, currency risks, and credit risks. a lower rate of return compared to fossil fuel projects and a higher risk of investment compared to fossil fuel projects and rapid technological advancements in the field of green energy are the major reasons for financial risks.⁶⁹
- **Environmental Risks:** Renewable energy projects can have environmental risks such as natural disasters, which can result in damage to infrastructure and equipment, and cause delays in project completion and cost overrun.⁷⁰

It is important to assess and mitigate these fiscal risks before investing in renewable energy projects. A thorough understanding of these risks can help investors make informed decisions and develop effective risk management strategies. These risk-factors can be categorized under two comprehensive fiscal risk terms: 1- stranded costs 2- stranded assets In the next section the implications for RE fiscal regime regarding these terms will be discussed.

3.2.1. Stranded costs

Stranded cost recovery is a term used in the energy industry to refer to the recovery of costs associated with investments in power generation assets that have become

⁶⁹ - Farhad Taghizadeh-Hesary and Naoyuki Yoshino, 'Sustainable solutions for green financing and investment in renewable energy projects' (2020) 13 *Energies* 788

⁷⁰ - Amirhossein Karamoozian and others, 'Risk assessment of renewable energy projects using uncertain information' (2022) 46 *International Journal of Energy Research* 18079 p. 18082

uneconomical due to changes in market conditions.⁷¹ In the context of renewable energy projects, stranded cost recovery may occur when a renewable energy project becomes uneconomical due to changes in government policy or market conditions. The recovery of these costs impacts the fiscal regimes of RE projects that cannot be covered by simple PFIT mechanisms or CfD contracts. As these methods only cover price risks and cannot dynamically adjust the fiscal terms based on the risks and expenditures that developers confront during the term of these contracts.

For example, suppose a utility invests in a new wind farm based on the assumption that it will receive a certain level of government subsidies for the energy it generates. However, if the government changes its policy and reduces or eliminates those subsidies, the wind farm may become uneconomical, and the utility may be left with stranded costs associated with the investment.

To recover these stranded costs, the utility may seek compensation from the government or other parties. It is common that utilities' stranded costs are calculated and a rate is added to the energy price so that utilities can recover the loss.⁷² In the case of renewable energy projects, stranded cost recovery may also involve the decommissioning or repurposing of the assets associated with the project. stranded cost recovery can be a complex issue that requires careful consideration of a variety of factors, including the nature of the investment, the market conditions at the time of the investment, and any changes in policy or other external factors that may impact the project's profitability. Here

⁷¹ - Nathan Paul Harnly, *Stranded costs and other economic challenges in electric utility restructuring* (WISE 1998) p.5

⁷² - Walter R Hall, 'Securitization and Stranded Cost Recovery' (1997) 18 Energy LJ 363

are brief examples of regulatory changes that resulted in stranded costs for renewable energy projects:

- Spain's retroactive subsidy cuts: In 2010, the Spanish government introduced a subsidy scheme to support renewable energy projects. However, in 2013, the government retroactively changed the subsidy scheme, reducing the subsidies available to existing renewable energy projects. This caused significant losses for investors, as many projects became uneconomical overnight.
- Germany's reduction of feed-in tariffs: In 2014, the German government reduced feed-in tariffs for solar photovoltaic (PV) projects. This led to a decrease in the profitability of existing solar PV projects, and many investors faced stranded costs as a result.
- Italy's changes to support schemes: In 2014, Italy introduced changes to its renewable energy support schemes. These changes included a reduction in feed-in tariffs for solar PV projects and a reduction in the amount of time that projects could receive subsidies. This led to significant losses for investors, as many projects became uneconomical.
- UK's early closure of renewable energy subsidy schemes: In 2015, the UK government announced that it would close its Renewables Obligation subsidy scheme early, from 2016 to 2017. This led to a rush to complete renewable energy projects before the scheme closed, and many projects were left stranded when the scheme ended earlier than expected.

As mentioned before, market conditions also can cause stranded costs in a renewable energy project. Here are some actual examples in this context:

- Solar power plants in California: In 2018, several large solar power plants in California faced stranded costs due to the abundance of low-cost solar energy in the state. As a result of the high levels of solar energy being produced, the market prices for electricity were driven down, making it difficult for the solar power plants to operate profitably.
- Wind farms in Brazil: In 2016, several wind farms in Brazil faced stranded costs due to a decrease in demand for energy and oversupply in the market. The wind farms had been built with the expectation of high energy prices and demand, but changes in market conditions led to a decrease in revenue and profitability.
- Biofuel production in the United States: In the early 2010s, several biofuel production companies in the United States faced stranded costs due to falling oil prices and changes in government policy. The companies had invested heavily in biofuel production, but the decline in oil prices made biofuels less competitive, and changes in government policy reduced the subsidies available to support the industry.

There are several methods for recovery of stranded costs such as contract renegotiation⁷³, asset repurposing⁷⁴, government support⁷⁵ and Sale of assets.⁷⁶ Nevertheless, in this research the focus is on avoiding and managing the risk through contractual fiscal regime adjustment.

3.2.2. *Stranded assets*

The concept of stranded asset is identical to that of stranded cost.⁷⁷ Stranded assets refer to investments in assets that lose their value or become obsolete before the end of their

⁷³ - If a project is facing stranded costs due to changes in market conditions, it may be possible to renegotiate contracts with suppliers or customers. For example, if a wind farm is facing lower revenue due to a decrease in energy prices, it may be possible to renegotiate power purchase agreements (PPAs) with utility companies to ensure a minimum revenue level.

⁷⁴ - In some cases, it may be possible to repurpose the assets of a renewable energy project to make them more profitable. For example, a solar power plant facing stranded costs due to low energy prices could potentially be repurposed as a battery storage facility, which could provide valuable grid services and revenue streams.

⁷⁵ - Governments may provide support to help recover stranded costs in renewable energy projects. This could include financial assistance, such as subsidies or tax credits, or policy changes to support the industry.

⁷⁶ - If a project is facing significant stranded costs and cannot be repurposed or renegotiated, it may be possible to sell the assets to another party. This could include selling the project to a new investor or selling the land and infrastructure for another use. William J Baumol and J Gregory Sidak, 'Stranded costs' (1994) 18 Harv JL & Pub Pol'y 835

⁷⁷ - They can be used interchangeably.

useful life, and they are a common risk in the energy industry.⁷⁸

In the case of renewable energy projects, stranded assets may occur if the project relies on outdated or inefficient technology, or if there is a sudden shift in market conditions or government policies that render the project uncompetitive. For example, if a wind farm is built in an area with high wind speeds, but later new technology enables wind turbines to be built in lower wind speed areas, the original wind farm may become a stranded asset.

Here are several actual examples of stranded assets in renewable energy sector:

- **Geothermal Power Plants in Germany:** In the early 2000s, several geothermal power plants were built in Germany, with the expectation that they would produce cheap and reliable energy. However, due to technical problems and the high cost of drilling, many of these plants were unable to meet their projected output, and they became stranded assets. Some of these plants were later dismantled and sold for scrap, resulting in significant losses for investors.
- **Concentrated Solar Power Plants in Spain:** In the late 2000s, Spain invested heavily in concentrated solar power (CSP) technology, with the construction of several large-scale CSP plants. However, due to changes in government policies and the emergence of cheaper photovoltaic (PV) solar technology, many of these plants were unable to compete in the

⁷⁸ - Kyra Bos and Joyeeta Gupta, 'Stranded assets and stranded resources: Implications for climate change mitigation and global sustainable development' (2019) 56 Energy Research & Social Science 101215

market, and they became stranded assets. Some of these plants were later sold for a fraction of their original cost.

- **Offshore Wind Farms in China:** In the early 2010s, China embarked on an ambitious plan to build offshore wind farms, with the goal of producing 5 GW of offshore wind energy by 2015. However, due to technical challenges and delays in grid infrastructure, many of these projects were unable to come online as planned, and they became stranded assets. Some of these projects were later abandoned, resulting in significant losses for investors.

These examples illustrate how stranded assets can occur in the renewable energy sector due to a range of factors, including technical challenges, changes in market conditions, and shifts in government policies. To mitigate the risk of stranded assets, renewable energy projects should carefully evaluate the feasibility and profitability of their investments and regularly assess their performance to ensure that they remain competitive and viable over the long term.⁷⁹

3.2.3. Expenditures

Planning a proper fiscal regime for renewable energy projects necessitates a thorough understanding of the costs involved. Accurate articulation and categorization of costs play a pivotal role in designing an effective fiscal framework that ensures financial viability, attracts investments, and promotes sustainable growth in the renewable energy sector. As an important parameter in the R-factor mechanism, this section explores the costs in

⁷⁹ - Ben Caldecott, 'Introduction to special issue: stranded assets and the environment' (2017) 7 *Journal of Sustainable Finance & Investment* 1

renewable energy projects, categorizing them into capital costs, non-capital costs, and operational costs.

Capital Costs (Capex): Effective planning of a fiscal regime requires a clear articulation of capital costs, which represent the initial investment required for the project. Articulating capital costs involves identifying and categorizing expenses related to renewable energy equipment, construction and installation, and land acquisition. These costs provide the foundation for the project's infrastructure and include components such as solar panels, wind turbines, foundation construction, electrical connections, and securing suitable land.⁸⁰

Non-Capital Costs (non-Capex): A well-designed fiscal regime should consider the articulation of non-capital costs, which are incurred during the project development and construction phases. Non-capital costs include expenses associated with development and permitting, engineering and design, and financing and transactions. Accurately articulating these costs involves assessing feasibility studies, environmental impact assessments, engineering and design fees, financial advisory expenses, legal fees, and insurance premiums.⁸¹

Operational Costs (Opex): To establish an effective fiscal regime, it is crucial to articulate operational costs that occur throughout the project's operational lifespan. Operational costs encompass operation and maintenance (O&M) expenses, monitoring and control system costs, and administrative and management expenditures. Proper

⁸⁰ - Cheuk Wing Lee and Jin Zhong, 'Financing and risk management of renewable energy projects with a hybrid bond' (2015) 75 *Renewable Energy* 779 p.780

⁸¹ - James Loewen, 'LCOE is an undiscounted metric that inaccurately disfavors renewable energy resources' (2020) 33 *The Electricity Journal* 106769

articulation of operational costs involves accounting for routine maintenance, repairs, inspections, personnel, monitoring systems, data collection equipment, project management, administrative staff and office expenses.⁸²

3.2.4. Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE)

The Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) is a metric used in the renewable energy sector to assess the cost of producing electricity over the entire lifetime of a power generation system, typically expressed in cents per kilowatt-hour (c/kWh) or dollars per megawatt-hour (\$/MWh). It allows for the comparison of different energy sources or technologies, considering both their initial capital costs and ongoing operational and maintenance expenses. Factors such as Capex, Opex, energy output, lifetime of the system, incentive rates and taxes are involved in determining LCOE for different RE projects.⁸³

The formula of LCOE is:

$$LCOE = \frac{\text{Total Present Value of Costs}}{\text{Total Present Value of Electricity Generated}}$$

The term "levelized" refers to the process of spreading or leveling the costs of electricity production over the entire lifetime of a power generation system. This is done

⁸² - M. O'Connor, T. Lewis and G. Dalton, 'Operational expenditure costs for wave energy projects and impacts on financial returns' (2013) 50 *Renewable Energy* 1119 p.1120

⁸³ - Wei Shen and others, 'A comprehensive review of variable renewable energy levelized cost of electricity' (2020) 133 *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 110301

to make a fair and accurate comparison of different energy sources with varying costs and lifespans.⁸⁴

Renewable energy systems typically have higher upfront capital costs but lower operating costs compared to conventional fossil fuel-based power plants. On the other hand, fossil fuel-based power plants have lower upfront capital costs but higher ongoing expenses for purchasing the fuel and maintenance. Furthermore, renewable energy sources exhibit varying lifespans when compared to traditional power plants. A crucial aspect to consider is that renewable energy plants with low LCOE might experience fluctuating energy output due to their intermittent nature, leading to challenges in integrating them into the grid. Conversely, conventional energy plants maintain a steady output, resulting in fewer concerns related to grid integration and transmission. Hence, in the energy market, RE prices may not always be more cost-effective than conventional energy prices, indicating that the RE market is not yet fully mature and requires governmental support schemes.⁸⁵

Clearly, the Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) serves as a comparative metric for different energy plants, but it fails to capture the dynamic actual costs involved in renewable energy (RE) projects. Consequently, the R-factor mechanism advocates using parameters that consider the economy of scale such as cumulative costs or marginal cost parameters rather than relying on LCOE.

⁸⁴ - Manasseh Obi and others, 'Calculation of levelized costs of electricity for various electrical energy storage systems' (2017) 67 *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 908

⁸⁵ - Thomas TD Tran and Amanda D Smith, 'Incorporating performance-based global sensitivity and uncertainty analysis into LCOE calculations for emerging renewable energy technologies' (2018) 216 *Applied energy* 157 p.164

3.2.5. Marginal cost

Marginal Cost (MC) represents the incremental costs incurred when producing an additional unit of a good or service. It is calculated by taking the total change in the cost (Total Cost, TC) of producing more goods and dividing that by the change in the number of goods (Quantity, Q) produced.⁸⁶

$$MC = \Delta TC / \Delta Q$$

Marginal cost plays a crucial role in the assessment and decision-making process of renewable energy projects. Proper consideration of marginal cost is essential for designing the contractual and fiscal terms that govern these projects. The typical cost functions determining marginal costs are either linear, quadratic, or cubic. Depending on the RE type, capital costs, operating and maintenance costs, variable costs caused by changes in weather conditions, Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE), economies of scale and technological advancements, the cost function in renewable energies is different. Nevertheless, as this research assumes high capital-intensive RE projects, the cost function cannot be linear or fixed during the production term.

In a linear cost function, the marginal cost remains constant as the level of output increases. The formula for marginal cost in a linear cost function is:

$$MC = b = \Delta TC / \Delta Q$$

Here, "b" represents the slope of the linear cost function. The constant marginal cost allows for straightforward planning and pricing decisions, as the cost per additional unit remains consistent.

⁸⁶ - A Araujo, 'Marginal Cost & its Variation in Different Economy Scales' (2019) 2 International Journal of Tax Economics and Management 29 p.29

Linear cost functions may not accurately reflect the cost structure of renewable energy projects, which often involve economies of scale, other price variables, peak and off-peak prices and other nonlinear cost relationships. In contrast, a quadratic cost function acknowledges the presence of economies of scale up to a certain level of output, beyond which costs increase at an accelerating rate. The formula for a quadratic cost function is:

$$TC = a + bQ + cQ^2$$

The marginal cost in a quadratic cost function is not constant and varies with the level of output. It can be calculated by taking the derivative of the cost function with respect to quantity ($MC = dTC/dQ$).⁸⁷ The inclusion of the quadratic term accounts for the increasing rate of cost growth at higher levels of production.

Moreover, cubic or exponential cost functions are occasionally employed to capture complex cost relationships in certain industries. An exponential cost function can be represented as:

$$TC = a * e^{(bQ)}$$

Here, "e" denotes the base of the natural logarithm. Exponential cost functions often reflect cost dynamics influenced by technological advancements, learning curves, or other factors. Thus, it indicates a weighted quadratic cost function.⁸⁸ Therefore, exponential cost functions may introduce additional complexities in terms of cost estimation and management regarding RE projects.

⁸⁷ - Tyrone E Duncan, 'Linear-exponential-quadratic Gaussian control' (2013) 58 IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control 2910

⁸⁸ - Jason L Speyer, C-H Fan and Ravi N Banavar, *Optimal stochastic estimation with exponential cost criteria* (IEEE 1992)

Various cost drivers impact marginal cost in renewable energy projects. Economies of scale play a significant role, allowing for reductions in marginal cost as the production scale increases. Factors like improved technology, enhanced resource utilization, and learning curve effects can lead to cost efficiencies and lower marginal costs over time. Conversely, input prices and regulatory requirements can influence marginal costs, potentially resulting in cost fluctuations. It is essential to consider these cost drivers when designing the contractual and fiscal terms for renewable energy projects.

Understanding and appropriately incorporating marginal cost into the contractual and fiscal terms of renewable energy projects are vital for financial planning, pricing strategies, and decision-making. Different cost functions, such as linear, quadratic, or exponential, provide alternative frameworks for analyzing cost dynamics and determining marginal cost. By considering the specific cost drivers and cost functions relevant to renewable energy projects, stakeholders can develop robust fiscal frameworks that support the long-term sustainability and profitability of renewable energy ventures.

Investment in renewable energies is profitable when the price for each unit of electricity is more than marginal cost. Therefore regulators consider / should take into account marginal cost factor when applying incentive rates. It has significant implications for just and affordable energy prices. Since marginal costs vary depending on different conditions, incentive rates must also change dynamically in response to this parameter. For example, if energy rates aren't flexible and dynamically changing, consumers will pay more for energy even in off-peak periods, because they've paid a rate based on marginal peak costs regardless of cost-function-changes during peak and off-

peak, which is unfair.⁸⁹ Moreover, it is difficult to determine predefined rates for different projects with different risk profiles and varying cost functions and cost drivers. Therefore, the contractual method is appropriate as it adapts to the characteristics of each specific project and can adjust the incentive rates with such dynamic parameters.

3.2.6. Maximum competitive price in the market

To ensure the profitability of renewable energy projects, it is essential to establish a price per kilowatt-hour (kWh) of electricity that exceeds the marginal cost. However, it is equally important to foster the growth of the renewable energy electricity market while maintaining competitiveness with fossil fuel-based electricity. Therefore, it becomes crucial to design incentives such as Feed-in Tariffs (FIT) or other forms of subsidies in a manner that prevents renewable energy prices from exceeding a reasonable competitive price in the market.

In a relatively liberalized electricity market, it is not usually allowed to set a cap price for the commodity. Nevertheless, there is/can be metrics that can identify a range of price for RE to be considered optimal and competitive with conventional energy sources.⁹⁰ the maximum competitive price represents the upper limit of price ranges across all energy sources, irrespective of their origin. This maximum price is determined independently of the specific energy source. However, if the market price is subject to

⁸⁹ - John T Wenders, 'Peak load pricing in the electric utility industry' (1976) *The Bell Journal of Economics* 232 and Lee S. Friedman, 'The importance of marginal cost electricity pricing to the success of greenhouse gas reduction programs' (2011) *39 Energy Policy* 7347

⁹⁰ - Yu-Chung Tsao, Thuy-Linh Vu and Jye-Chyi Lu, 'Pricing, capacity and financing policies for investment of renewable energy generations' (2021) *303 Applied Energy* 117664

direct regulation, the highest permissible price is set as the ceiling, beyond which prices cannot exceed.

The goal is to strike a balance between incentivizing renewable energy development by ensuring prices cover costs (marginal cost) while also considering market competitiveness. By keeping renewable energy prices within the bounds of the maximum competitive price, the renewable energy sector can thrive and coexist with conventional fossil fuel-based electricity generation. Therefore, in addition to the marginal cost, another parameter that must be included in the R-factor mechanism is the maximum competitive electricity price.

In the context of determining the maximum competitive electricity price, various approaches can be employed depending on the regulatory framework and market structure. In liberalized electricity markets, the maximum competitive price is typically established through market-based pricing mechanisms. Participants engage in competitive bidding or participate in wholesale electricity markets, where prices are determined by the interplay of supply and demand forces. For renewable energy, the LCOE metric plays a determining role in RE pricing.⁹¹ The highest accepted or observed price within this competitive process serves as the maximum competitive price. In regulated markets, the determination of the maximum competitive price falls under the purview of regulatory oversight. Regulatory authorities assess factors such as production costs, infrastructure investments, operation and maintenance expenses, time of use (ToU)

⁹¹ - Maira Bruck, Peter Sandborn and Navid Goudarzi, 'A Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) model for wind farms that include Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs)' (2018) 122 *Renewable Energy* 131

and reasonable profit margins for generators.⁹² Additionally, price caps may be imposed to safeguard consumers and prevent excessive pricing. The goal of assessing and determining the maximum competitive price is to strike a balance between consumer protection, investment encouragement, and market competition. The specific approach used is influenced by jurisdictional considerations and policy objectives, ultimately aiming to foster a sustainable and competitive electricity market.

It is highlighted that the maximum price in a liberalized market is a dynamic number that changes over the course of the RE project. Therefore, the maximum price is not a fixed rate. Regulatory organs cannot continually adjust incentive rates for RE investment to adapt to these changes, which may impact each project differently, so a contractual tool is needed to adjust the fiscal regime. Not using such tools can be the reason a regulatory change in FIT rates usually renders some RE projects unprofitable.

3.3. R-Factor mechanism

The concept of the R-factor has long been recognized as a valuable tool in the design and adjustment of contractual fiscal regimes. Traditionally, this concept has predominantly flourished within the context of upstream petroleum contracts, where it has played a crucial role in balancing the interests of resource developers and host governments.⁹³ However, as the world undergoes a transition towards renewable energy sources, there is

⁹² - Joseph P Tomain, 'The past and future of electricity regulation' (2002) 32 *Envtl L* 435, and Md Pauzi Abdullah and others, 'Optimizing time of use (ToU) electricity pricing in regulated market' (2016) 78 *Jurnal Teknologi* 49

⁹³ - Ebrahimi and Maddahinasab, 'Controlling Contractor's Rate of Return (ROR) in Risk Service Contracts with R-Factor Mechanism'

a growing need to explore innovative approaches that can effectively adapt fiscal regimes to suit the unique characteristics of renewable energy projects.

In the realm of upstream petroleum contracts, the R-factor has proven instrumental in capturing the dynamic nature of resource extraction and revenue generation. This factor, typically defined as the ratio of cumulative receipts to cumulative costs, enables contract parties to monitor and adjust fiscal terms over the project's lifecycle. It serves as an indicator of the economic viability of the project and helps balance the interests of investors and governments. The literature surrounding the R-factor in petroleum contracts has witnessed significant advancements, with various models and formulas proposed to effectively incorporate this concept into contractual frameworks.⁹⁴

While the R-factor has been extensively explored in the petroleum industry, its application within the renewable energy sector remains relatively underdeveloped. As renewable energy sources become increasingly prevalent and economically competitive, there is a pressing need to tailor fiscal regimes to encourage investment and ensure the sustainable growth of the sector. By adopting the R-factor concept and adapting it to the unique characteristics of renewable energy projects, we can establish a more robust contractual framework that aligns the interests of project developers, investors, and governments.

In the context of renewable energy, the R-factor can be redefined to reflect the financial gain and loss experienced throughout the project's lifecycle. By considering factors such as FIT rates, risk factors and costs, the R-factor formula can be modified to

⁹⁴ - Maddahinasab, 'Fiscal analysis of new Iranian petroleum contract called IPC from a legal and contractual perspective'

capture the revenue generated relative to the costs incurred keeping the price for RE in a competitive range in relation to conventional energy price. This adjustment allows for a dynamic evaluation of the project's financial performance and serves as a mechanism to adjust the fiscal regime accordingly. By ensuring that the FIT rate or price in PPAs remain above the marginal cost yet within the range of maximum competitive market price, the adjusted fiscal regime strikes a balance between incentivizing renewable energy development and maintaining competitiveness within the electricity market.

The distinction between the R-factor and FIT lies in their respective roles and applications within the context of renewable energy projects. The R-factor serves as a contractual tool that is specifically tailored to individual projects, taking into account their unique characteristics and financial parameters. It captures the cumulative financial performance of a project by considering factors such as receipts, costs, and risk scores. In contrast, FIT (feed-in-tariff) is a regulatory tool implemented by governing bodies to incentivize renewable energy production. It sets a predetermined rate at which renewable energy producers are compensated for the electricity they generate and feed into the grid. FIT rates are typically standardized and applicable across multiple projects, aiming to promote the development of renewable energy at a broader scale. While FIT offers a general framework for supporting renewable energy, the R-factor provides a more project-specific approach, allowing for a customized assessment of financial performance and the adjustment of fiscal terms accordingly. Thus, the R-factor offers a greater level of flexibility and adaptability to the unique circumstances of each renewable energy project, making it a valuable contractual tool in optimizing financial outcomes. And the function of R-factor is that it adjusts the regulatory rates such as FIT in a dynamic way.

Comparing the R-factor mechanism to the pricing mechanism in PPAs, there are/can be similar functions. In PPAs there is either a fixed price agreed upon for kWh of

electricity or a variable price.⁹⁵ Or a combination of both as the hybrid pricing method. The hybrid pricing model ensures a minimum price for renewable energy (RE) generation that slightly exceeds the marginal cost. This safeguard guarantees the profitability of the RE project even if the actual market price falls below this minimum.⁹⁶ Furthermore, when the market price exceeds the minimum, the project's rate of return proportionally rises. To maintain affordability for consumers, CfDs have been implemented, making sellers to pass on excess profits to the regulator or utility, thereby ensuring a reasonable final price for consumers. Consequently, with a CfD, the sellers' rate of return remains fixed. However, with the fixed ROR, producers lack the incentive to invest in technology updates and take on additional risks. Because that results in increased total costs without a corresponding increase in the minimum guaranteed price, potentially leading to financial losses.⁹⁷ The hybrid pricing model strikes a balance between the limitations of fixed pricing, which may not suit larger and riskier RE projects, and the risks associated with variable pricing without proper caution.⁹⁸ Hence, for such RE projects, the hybrid

⁹⁵ - In variable pricing, the cost of electricity in the PPA is tied to prevailing market rates or specific indices, such as wholesale electricity prices or natural gas prices.

⁹⁶ - Chenghui Tang and Fan Zhang, 'Classification, principle and pricing manner of renewable power purchase agreement' (IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science)

⁹⁷ - May, Neuhoff and Richstein, 'Affordable electricity supply via contracts for difference for renewable energy'

⁹⁸ - Bruck, Sandborn and Goudarzi, 'A Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) model for wind farms that include Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs)'

pricing model proves to be an appropriate and well-suited approach.⁹⁹The hybrid pricing mechanism can be enhanced by incorporating the R-factor mechanism, which dynamically formulates the price with each purchase invoice. This additional mechanism allows for the inclusion of various parameters that boost investors' rate of return, encouraging greater investments and the adoption of updated technology. Consequently it can align different RE projects with the applied energy policies and strategies.

In the next sections several basic models of R-factor for renewable energies will be discussed to elaborate how such mechanism can dynamically sync different RE projects to dynamic market or policy changes.

3.3.1. Price-based R-factor

In a price-based R-factor model, the objective is to sync the FIT rate, variable price rate in a PPA or the rate of subsidies within a range that price paid for each unit of electricity is above marginal cost and equal/below the maximum price. The model for this R-factor formula is:

$$R \text{ factor} = \frac{\text{Cumulative production} \times \text{Maximum price}}{\text{Cumulative production} \times \text{Marginal cost}}$$

Cumulative production is the total quantity of electricity units produced over the specified period. Maximum price is the highest possible competitive price per unit of electricity in the market. Marginal cost is the cost of producing one additional unit of electricity.

⁹⁹ - For small or local RE projects such as small solar or wind energy plants that have a very low LCOE with a marginal cost near zero, a fixed price model in PPA is enough. Nevertheless, for more ambitious projects with heavy investment, a hybrid pricing mechanism is necessary.

The numerator, (Cumulative Production $\times$ Maximum Price), represents the total revenue generated by selling all the units of electricity at the maximum price. The denominator, (Cumulative Production $\times$ Marginal Cost), represents the total cost incurred to produce all the units of electricity at the marginal cost.

By comparing these two measurements, the R-factor assesses the financial gain or loss relative to the cost of production and the maximum price. If the R-factor is greater than 1, it indicates that the cumulative revenue from selling electricity at the maximum price exceeds the cumulative cost of production at the marginal cost. This implies a favorable financial situation. If the R-factor is less than 1, it suggests that the cumulative cost of production at the marginal cost exceeds the cumulative revenue from selling electricity at the maximum price. This implies an unfavorable financial situation. Accordingly, the incentive mechanism (FIT rate or subsidy rate or simply the PPA price) must be adjusted accordingly. Therefore, when R-factor is less than 1, the incentive rate must increase to the point that by applying it to the formula, R-factor exceeds 1 slightly. The increase in the incentive rates must restore equilibrium to the investor's ROR. Additionally, if the initial R-factor is more than 1, so that even if the project is not benefited by the incentive rates, it still exceeds 1, then the incentive rate should be zero. That entails selling the electricity generated at a competitive price to the end users And keeping RE project's ROR controlled within a fair range.¹⁰⁰

This represents the fundamental R-factor formula when integrating the generated energy into the grid. However, there is potential to enhance the formula by introducing additional parameters to align the fiscal terms of each transaction with various influencing

¹⁰⁰ - Ebrahimi and Maddahinasab, 'Controlling Contractor's Rate of Return (ROR) in Risk Service Contracts with R-Factor Mechanism'

factors. For instance, when the access to the grid is limited or in the context of Renewable Portfolio Standards (RPS) mechanisms, the quantity of purchased electricity significantly impacts the projects' Return on Revenue (ROR).¹⁰¹ Therefore, it becomes essential to factor in the quantities of purchase into the equation.¹⁰² Consequently, this approach adjusts the price rate, resulting in an increase for utilities with smaller purchase quantities and a decrease for those with larger quantities. The ultimate aim is to achieve a consistent ROR for the seller across transactions with varying purchase quantities.

3.3.2. Risk/Performance-based R factor

The R-factor formula can vary depending on the objectives pursued by the authorities in renewable energy (RE) generation. The previous formula, known as the price-based R-factor, is suitable for typical scenarios where the generated electricity is intended for grid integration and consumption by end users. However, for cases involving alternative uses like green hydrogen production, a Risk/Performance-based R-factor is suitable. Here, the primary goal is maximizing RE production, and the adjustment of incentives based on market prices is not necessary. Nonetheless, it remains crucial to consider the risk factor and production performance, ensuring that projects with optimal output are encouraged, and investors are motivated to invest more and assume higher risks for better returns. To fulfill this objective, I propose the following basic R-factor model:

$$R \text{ factor} = \frac{\text{Cumulative Production/Risk Score}}{\text{Cumulative costs}}$$

¹⁰¹ - Jenny S Heeter, Bethany K Speer and Mark B Glick, *International best practices for implementing and designing renewable portfolio standard (RPS) policies*, 2019) p.10

¹⁰² - This can be done by replacing the cumulative production with the actual quantity of the transaction in the formula.

In this equation, the R-factor represents the project's performance despite the risks involved. And by dividing the ratio by the incurred costs, it indicates the optimality of the project over a specific course of time (the project term). Depending on the factors that result in stranded assets or costs, the risk score can be determined. For example, a project may bravely use a large amount of assets that may become obsolete in the upcoming years. However, by using a significant number of solar panels as an example, investors generate a large amount of electricity despite the risks. Therefore, taking such a risk must be rewarded. Contrary to the previous R-factor model, in this model, the incentive rate, such as FITs or the price for purchasing electricity, increases when the R-factor exceeds 1. For that purpose, an adjustment table must be negotiated so that it determines for each R-factor level how much the incentive rate increases. Below is a straightforward illustrative table demonstrating the adjustments using assumed numerical values:

R-factor	Price per kWh
Less than 1	1€
1	1.2€
2	1.5€
3	1.8€
4	2.1€

In a real-world project, the involved parties in the contract (such as a PPA) engage in negotiations to determine the desired rate of return levels. Consequently, the specific values for this table will be established based on mutual agreement and in accordance with the negotiated terms. Using this formula prevents developers from goldplating, since extra expenditure is only rewarded with higher ROR if it results in increased energy generation.

An R-factor mechanism alone cannot secure dynamic fiscal regime adjustments. Therefore, R-factor needs to be supported and promoted within a structure that guarantees its function. For that some supporting contractual tools are necessary which are discussed in the following chapter.

4. Necessary contractual tools for dynamic fiscal regime adjustment

In the previous sections, I provided an in-depth exploration of the interplay between fiscal terms in renewable energy (RE) projects and the regulatory incentive rates, achieved through the innovative R-factor mechanism. However, for these fiscal terms to be effectively functional and aligned with energy-related regulations and legislations, additional contractual institutions are required. This chapter further discusses the Joint Management Committee (JMC) mechanism, a proven approach utilized in upstream petroleum projects for dynamic project management. Additionally, I will explore essential contractual clauses that facilitate the application of the R-factor to adjust regulatory and legislative rules, ensuring they are congruent with the unique requirements of RE projects.

4.1. Joint management committee

The Joint Management Committee (JMC) is a crucial element that promotes effective decision-making and coordination in the execution of projects. By employing this mechanism, stakeholders involved in the RE project can collaboratively address challenges, assess risks, and implement dynamic strategies to ensure the project's success. Drawing inspiration from its successful application in upstream petroleum projects, we can adapt the JMC model to suit the unique characteristics of RE projects, fostering a cohesive and adaptive approach to project management.

The petroleum industry is a huge, complex, and multifaceted sector. Oil and gas companies are involved in a large number of daily transactions around the world. Each of these transactions results in some form of agreement or contract that involves large sums of money, risks, and liabilities. Therefore, the Petroleum sector has been subjected to the most significant international agreements and disputes. Many of the legal doctrines in

international commerce law have been developed in response to the arrangements by which oil and gas have been extracted and sold.¹⁰³

When it comes to contracts, companies, and markets, the petroleum industry is perhaps the most advanced. Since the lease issued in 1857 to Colonel Drake in Titusville, Pennsylvania until now this industry has come a long way building the norms, institutions, and market structures of an internationally soft-regulated business.¹⁰⁴ Thus, nowadays, the term '*Lex Petrolea*' is a famous and meaningful concept in this industry that refers to the norms and mechanisms mostly accepted by the international and national companies in this sector.¹⁰⁵ Although, there are some writers who may doubt the existence of *Lex Petrolea* arguing that there is not enough evidence backing this concept.¹⁰⁶ This critic of *Lex Petrolea* expects it to be a rigid form of regulation. In that sense, *Lex Petrolea* may not meet the criteria for being a solid legal subject. Nevertheless, as there are specific norms and structures that have evolved within this sector, *Lex Petrolea* could be considered at least as a soft legal source.¹⁰⁷

¹⁰³ - A Timothy Martin, 'Model Contracts: A Survey of the Global Petroleum Industry' (2004) 22 *Journal of Energy & Natural Resources Law* 281. P. 281

¹⁰⁴ - Kim Talus, Scott Looper and Steven Otilar, 'Lex Petrolea and the internationalization of petroleum agreements: focus on Host Government Contracts' (2012) 5 *The Journal of World Energy Law & Business* 181. P. 186

¹⁰⁵ - Mostapha Maddahinasab and others, 'Managing confidential information on petroleum projects in the case of third parties' (2019) *Energy Policy Studies* . P. 50

¹⁰⁶ - Terence Daintith, 'Against 'lex petrolea'' (2017) 10 *The Journal of World Energy Law & Business* 1

¹⁰⁷ - As norms and methods that are not mandatory but they are followed anyway.

One of the mechanisms that has been developed within petroleum contracts is the joint management committee (JMC). In the earlier, more prosperous era of petroleum exploration, only concessions were used, which are now referred to as traditional concessions. The traditional concessions, especially those in the Middle East were very favorable for International Oil Companies (IOCs). The conventional oil concessions contained very few, if any, obligations for IOCs. They only had to pay a royalty to the host states. The rest of the project, production, work program, and the technology in use was up to the IOCs themselves.¹⁰⁸ Thus, as host states had no role in the projects, no JMC mechanism was considered in the traditional concessions unless there was a joint venture (JV) between some IOCs. In that case, there would be an operating committee between them that had a similar function as JMC. .¹⁰⁹

In the post-World War II era, when traditional concessions were seen as unfavorable for host states, nationalism movements led to the rejection of traditional concessions, gradually replaced by modern concessions that include more obligations for IOCs and more supervision and inspection rights for the host countries. To be able to exert more control over IOCs, some countries have applied risk-service contracts in which IOCs act as contractors working on behalf of the National Oil Companies (NOCs). Additionally, some other host states opted for Production Sharing Contracts (PSAs), a contract that has characteristics of both risk service contracts and modern concessions.¹¹⁰

¹⁰⁸ - Talus, Looper and Otilar, 'Lex Petrolea and the internationalization of petroleum agreements: focus on Host Government Contracts'. P. 186

¹⁰⁹ - JMC term is mostly applied when the host state is also involved.

¹¹⁰ - Talus, Looper and Otilar, 'Lex Petrolea and the internationalization of petroleum agreements: focus on Host Government Contracts' pp. 186-188

Moreover, as other industries relied on carbon energy, the petroleum industry had to develop increasingly. That required more investments and taking more risks, which led to using more JVs and Joint Operation Agreements (JOAs) in most of the upstream projects.¹¹¹ Ongoing developments in the oil sector and updates on the contracts required an integrated strategy for better management of the projects. To meet this need, thus, JMC was developed.

Petroleum contracts usually set out that the parties to the contract must form a JMC after a specific period of time from the date of the contract being in force. This period of time may vary in each contract ranging from 30 days to 90 days since the contract's effective date. As an example, the PSA model in Cambodia stipulates that within 60 days of the effective date, a JMC shall be established. Under the Iraq model of oil risk-service contracts, JMC is to be established only 30 days after the effective date. This committee usually consists of an equal number of members from both parties to the contract. For example, in the Iraq's service contract model, the owner (Iraqi NOC) nominates four members including the chairman of the committee. And the contractor also nominates four members for the JMC. In service contracts and PSAs, the host states or NOCs have more power than contractors' representatives because they are the owners of the project and its production. Thus, the JMC's decisions in these contracts are required to be approved by the representative of the host state. On the contrary, in modern concessions, IOCs have the upper hand in JMC, as they own the project and the produced oil. Therefore, in the JMCs within concessions, although host states participate in making

¹¹¹ - Peter Roberts, *Joint Operating Agreements: A Practical Guide* (Globe law and business 2010) p. 16

decisions as far as they are related to their benefits, they are not in a position to confirm the decisions.

JMC makes all major decisions regarding the management of the petroleum operations including approval of all major expenditures, evaluation of the results of the exploration, planning and drilling of wells, and determination of the commerciality of the drilling results.¹¹² Generally, the functions and duties of JMCs include planning the work programs and budget, reviewing progress of the operator's work, supervising terms of contracts to be executed, resolving problems arising in petroleum operations, supervising and inspecting the operations. Regarding the different aspects of petroleum projects, a JMC may have different subcommittees concerning technical, financial, economic, social and environmental issues.¹¹³ Typically, a JMC in a petroleum project has a technical subcommittee for dealing with technical issues, a budget subcommittee to analyse the proposed annual work program and budget. Audit subcommittee to inspect and supervise operator expenditures in accordance with the approved annual work program and budget. Subcommittee for marketing and financial matters.

4.1.1. JMC design for RE projects

Considering the risks in the renewable energy market sector and contracts that are applied in this section, a design for a JMC in an integrated renewable energy contract frame will be presented. It is first necessary to determine what kind of RE system can contain that. JMC, could be applied when there is a large RE project that requires heavy and

¹¹² - DR Jennings, JB Feiten and HR Bock, *Petroleum accounting Principles, Procedures and Issues* (5th edn, Professional Development Institute 2000) p. 613

¹¹³ - Johnston, *International Petroleum Fiscal Systems-PSCs* p. 170

incremental risk-taking investment, in which case the government is participating in the project. For example, there is a BOT contract between a RE producer and the government (or related utilities) to construct and operate an offshore wind plant or extensive solar plants. The government may provide the producer with a PFIT, or there are predetermined utilities that purchase electricity from the RE project based on a non-fixed charge or incentive PPA format. In such RE system it is vital to keep the project profitable while competing with cheaper electricity. That means, although the price for the electricity produced from RE must be more than marginal costs, it also needs to be low enough to be able to compete with other sources of energy. To reach this goal, a solid, integrated collaboration is needed between certain participants in the RE project. RE JMCs are tasked with providing this collaboration framework.

It is important to highlight that every RE project requires its dedicated JMC focused solely on that specific venture and tailored to its distinctive risk profile. It should be emphasized that a single JMC does not govern all RE projects.

In the following section, the features of such JMCs will be discussed.

4.1.1.1. The participants in JMCs

The main participants of a JMC are representatives of the government, the RE producer company (developer/operator) and the utilities that in any case can be experts in different relevant fields such as regulations, finance, planning and environment etc. Also, in some cases there could be representatives from the grid owners and companies that facilitate power transmission and also companies that are in the battery sector, as their collaboration

and involvement in the RE project can be inevitable.¹¹⁴

The government's representatives may be experts from the energy ministry or the public utility company that regulates the (renewable) energy sector. In the JMC for a RE project, the government's representatives mainly are to secure the public policies and government's contractual obligations and rights being held properly in accordance with the efficient management of the project. Between the government and operator (RE producer) can be two contractual relationships. The first is the construction of a RE plant, and then it is more probable that the final owner of the project is a host government. Then there will either be a BOT or an EPCM between the host government and the producer. Also a PFIT which regulates the producer's rate of return (ROR). Thus the PFIT has a direct effect on the BOT/EPCM fiscal regime. On the other hand, between the government and utilities that buy energy from the RE project, there are regulatory relations such as requiring the utilities to buy electricity from the RE plant at a price rate adjusted dynamically by the R-factor formula. In this context, there could be green certificates or renewable portfolio standards (RPS) obligations between the government and utilities that need to be adjusted between them in the JMC. RPS is also a famous public RE policy that has been applied in the USA energy system. Based on this mechanism, utilities are obliged to provide a certain portion of their capacity through purchasing power from RE producers.¹¹⁵

¹¹⁴ - Shrestha and Ogunlan, 'Comparative study of Power Purchase Agreements in the Nepalese environment'

¹¹⁵ - Claire E Kreycik, Toby D Couture and Karlynn S Cory, *Procurement options for new renewable electricity supply*, 2011) pp. 1-2

Moreover, the government's representatives possess the authority to oversee activities governed by renewable energy (RE) regulations, including strict competition regulations in certain countries. Additionally, they are responsible for closely monitoring other regulations, contractual terms, and the adherence to obligations by all involved parties, ensuring the prevention of disputes and deadlocks during the RE project's execution. Furthermore, the JMC assumes a crucial role in effectively supervising environmental protection measures throughout the entire project duration, not solely limited to the project's commencement. In this capacity, JMCs demonstrate remarkable effectiveness in promoting various aspects of energy justice beyond just transactional energy justice..

The main relationship between the utility and the producer is the power purchase agreement (PPA), which establishes a long-term plan for purchasing power based on the R-factor price formula to reduce market risks. Hedging contracts can be embedded in the PPA with the format of hedging clauses. For example, options to buy or sell electricity (call / put options) at a certain price can be embedded in a PPA as well. Thus, the holder of an option is able to exercise it depending on the market situation and the fluctuations in the spot market price. Hence, a lot of future disputes and bottlenecks resulting from volatile electricity prices will be avoided.¹¹⁶

A JMC in this context can be very helpful as it provides a regular setting to adjust the PPA's fiscal regime and its hedging strategies.

4.1.1.2. Functions of the JMC

¹¹⁶ - Rajnish Kamat and Shmuel S Oren, 'Exotic options for interruptible electricity supply contracts' (2002) 50 Operations Research 835, p. 837

Power production output in RE sector is highly variable compared to fossil fuel based power. This variability is based on various time scales ranging from hourly, daily, and monthly to annually. In the case the share of RE electricity in the energy portfolio is not significantly high this uncertainty does not form a big problem, however, as governments aim for higher clean energy share (at least 20-30 %) this issue can become very challenging. Uncertainty and limited accuracy in RE production, limitations on the transmission system, increased need for reserves and impact of unpredicted large ramps, conflicting benefits of the participants in the RE market and coordination with the regulatory agencies are amongst the most demanding issues of RE projects. Although to some extent, these issues can be handled by a proper, large-scale electricity storage project. Nonetheless, regarding the current state of energy technology, that requires massive capital costs. Therefore, it is necessary for RE projects to have a ready and regular structure for coordination between the participants to bring about the most efficient decision regarding freshly updates in the RE market so that the mentioned risk can be properly managed.¹¹⁷ The assumed JMC must be capable of achieving this goal.

Also the JMCs in RE projects must provide an efficient procedure for the governments to supervise over the RE project and the relevant markets. Usually, one of the most annoying and discouraging elements in RE sector is the frequent regulatory decisions that affect the projects and markets. However, governments, by applying such policies are trying to promote RE sector, nevertheless, as the decisions are applied on a general level, it makes regulatory risks for both the producers and the utilities. Moreover, bureaucracy will slow down the sector. One of the most important functions of RE

¹¹⁷ - Eilyan Bitar and others, *Optimal contracts for wind power producers in electricity markets* (IEEE 2010) p. 1920

project's JMC is to provide a dynamic setting for the public/governmental representatives to supervise the projects and provide them with the support that they need.

Another function that the designated JMC must provide is to provide each RE project with annual work and budget plans in a way that they get in alignment with the long-term goals of the governments in the energy mix. Thus, in each year, goals and plans will be drawn and it will be decided how the capital for the expenditures needed for the goals are going to be supplied. These capitals may be provided by different methods such as financing, income from the project through the selling of the produced electricity and subsidies from the government. The JMC also must provide an auditing setting to make sure that the cash flow of the project is in the optimized balance and providing the procedure with a transparency needed for such projects.

Moreover, the JMC in a RE project is to provide a structure in which the contractual fiscal regimes in the different contracts involved in the project (construction, PFIT and PPA) are adjusted according to the facts and risks in the project and also according to the regulatory fiscal regime such as taxes and tariffs in any case that is relevant.

Another function of the JMC is to provide the RE projects with a regular and dynamic technical and technological assessment in order to apply the newest technologies in the project so that it can stabilize against the risks.

4.1.1.3. Format of the JMC

As a JMC in a RE project involves more participants from different sides, the format of the JMC is a key element in achieving the goals. Therefore, it must include different subcommittees that deal with different issues based on timely plans. For example there must be a subcommittee for pricing the power sold in different markets (forward market

or spot market) thus such subcommittee must hold session on daily basis to meet the needs for efficiency in the price risk management. Although holding a session and making decisions every day is difficult, nonetheless, it can be assigned to a subcommittee formed by experts from participating sides that is regulated by the JMC in its main yearly or quarterly sessions. Also there can be other subcommittees in other demanding issues of a RE project such as adjusting the fiscal regimes, technical issues such as transmission and energy storage etc.

The main JMC session can be held yearly or quarterly depending on the characteristics of each RE project. Exceptional sessions can be held in urgent cases following predetermined procedures.

Like the functions and qualifications of JMC, the format and procedures of it must be stipulated in the contracts that bind the participants in a RE project. These obligations and contractual terms can be added to the contracts under a section or clause relating JMC.

4.1.2. Comparison with regulatory committees

Depending on the style of government and public policies, JMCs in each host state can be subject to a higher public/supervisory/regulatory organ. The main functional difference between JMC and such organs is that each JMC is objectively engaged with its unique RE project, thus can provide in depth support and coordination for each specific project while the regulatory committees can only have subjective supervision and decision making that is applied to different projects. And concerning the format, while the regulatory committees/organs are related to the governments on a macro-level, JMCs are joint decision making structures on the micro-level of the RE projects that bring the specific participants of each RE project together. Thus, the existence of such a structure

is justified and needed for enhancement of RE production/consumption.

4.2. Stabilization and renegotiation clauses

In the dynamic and ever-evolving landscape of renewable energy projects, ensuring financial viability and stability is paramount. As governments worldwide respond to changing energy demands and environmental imperatives, fiscal regimes governing renewable energy investments are subject to frequent revisions.¹¹⁸ To navigate these uncertainties and create a flexible environment for adaptation, the use of stabilization clauses and renegotiation clauses has emerged as essential contractual tools. These mechanisms provide a means for parties involved in renewable energy projects to proactively manage the impact of fiscal term changes and foster a dynamic setting for the adjustment of fiscal regimes.

In this section, I delve into the significance of stabilization clauses and renegotiation clauses as indispensable contractual tools in renewable energy projects. I examine how these mechanisms contribute to creating a dynamic and flexible environment for adjusting fiscal regimes, particularly as supporting function for the proposed R-factor mechanism. Thus, I explore the benefits, challenges, and best practices in leveraging these contractual tools to promote long-term sustainability and successful project outcomes in the ever-evolving renewable energy sector.

4.2.1. Stabilization Clauses in Renewable Energy Projects

Stabilization clauses are contractual tools employed in various industries more

¹¹⁸ - Nicolae Marinescu, 'Changes in renewable energy policy and their implications: The case of Romanian producers' (2020) 13 *Energies* 6493

specifically international long-term projects¹¹⁹, including renewable energy projects, to manage regulatory risks and promote stability for investors. These clauses aim to protect the interests of parties involved by mitigating the potential adverse effects of changing laws, regulations, or fiscal regimes.¹²⁰ There is already enough literature on the concept and application of stabilization clauses either in general or in particular case of clean energy.¹²¹ In this section I review the philosophy, conventional form, and modern concept of stabilization clauses. Then regarding their specific application in renewable energy projects, I will reflect and articulate on the function of stabilization clauses as a necessary tool that sets the background up for adjusting the fiscal regime in RE projects using my proposed R-factor models.

Stabilization clauses reflect a fundamental principle of current foreign investment law, seeking to provide certainty and stability in the face of changing legal and regulatory environments. These clauses are designed to ensure that the rights and obligations of parties involved remain unchanged, to a reasonable extent, even if the governing laws or regulations are modified after the agreement's execution. The primary objective is to

¹¹⁹ - AFM Maniruzzaman, 'Drafting stabilisation clauses in international energy contracts: some pitfalls for the unwary' (2007) 5 Oil, Gas & Energy Law

¹²⁰ - Evaristus Oshionebo, 'Stabilization clauses in natural resource extraction contracts: legal, economic and social implications for developing countries' (2010) 10 *Asper Rev Int'l Bus & Trade L* 1

¹²¹ - Gillian Moon, 'Arrested ambition? Foreign investor protections, stabilization clauses and fossil-fuelled power generation in developing countries' (2021) 30 *Review of European, Comparative & International Environmental Law* 313 p.315

protect the expectations and investments of investors and create a stable environment conducive to long-term project development.¹²²

Traditionally, stabilization clauses have taken the form of "freezing clauses" or "standstill clauses." Freezing clauses freeze the legal and regulatory framework as it existed at the time of signing the agreement, preventing subsequent changes from affecting the contractual relationship.¹²³ Standstill clauses, on the other hand, typically require the government to maintain existing regulations and refrain from implementing new ones that could harm the investor's interests.¹²⁴ These conventional stabilization clauses primarily focus on maintaining the stability and predictability of legal and regulatory conditions. Nevertheless, as it does not make sense that a contract clause impact legislative and regulatory system, nowadays these conceptions of stabilization clauses are abandoned And there is a new understanding of stabilization clauses.

The modern concept of a stabilization clause refers to the obligation of the governmental party within a contract to reestablish the equilibrium of the contract that has become unbalanced as a result of legislative or regulatory changes. Consequently, the new application of the stabilization clauses does not claim to limit the authoritative organs, but rather to adapt the contract dynamically to changes in regulations, so that the

¹²² - Katarina Tomic, 'Stabilization Clauses in Energy Sector' (2020) *Harmonius: J Legal & Soc Stud Se Eur* 258

¹²³ - Jernej Letnar Čerňič, 'Corporate human rights obligations under stabilization clauses' (2010) *11 German Law Journal* 210 p.214

¹²⁴ - Peter J Walsh Jr, 'Standstill Agreements: Enterra Validates the Use of Standstill Agreements to Govern Minority Investment Programs' (1985) *42 Wash & Lee L Rev* 1015

previous distribution of rights and obligations (or economic rents) is reinstated within the current structure of governing laws.¹²⁵

In the context of renewable energy projects, stabilization clauses can be used to manage the risk associated with changes in the fiscal regime. Governments may alter tax laws, subsidies, feed-in tariffs, or other financial incentives, potentially affecting the profitability and viability of renewable energy investments. Stabilization clauses can provide investors with reassurance and mitigate the uncertainty caused by such changes.

Renewable energy stabilization clauses may stipulate that the fiscal regime in effect at the time of contract signing will remain applicable for a certain period or for the duration of the project. In some cases, they may require compensation or adjustments to the terms if the fiscal regime changes significantly. These clauses serve to protect investors from adverse financial consequences resulting from retroactive changes or unforeseen modifications to tax or subsidy schemes.¹²⁶

While stabilization clauses have the potential to manage regulatory and legislative risk in renewable energy projects, their effectiveness is subject to certain challenges and limitations. One challenge lies in striking the right balance between protecting investors' interests and ensuring governments' policy flexibility to respond to changing circumstances. Governments may argue that such clauses limit their ability to implement necessary policy adjustments in the renewable energy sector. Nonetheless, as modern

¹²⁵ - Katja Gehne and Romulo Brillo, *Stabilization clauses in international investment law: beyond balancing and fair and equitable treatment* (Institute of Economic Law, Transnational Economic Law Research Center 2017) p.8

¹²⁶ - Amélie Noilhac, 'Renewable energy investment cases against Spain and the quest for regulatory consistency' (2020) 71 *Questions of International Law* 21

definition of these clauses does not limit governments in changing the regulations, this challenge no longer exists. Moreover, the enforceability of stabilization clauses can vary across jurisdictions, particularly in cases where changing the contractual terms for reestablishing economic equilibrium is opposed by public interest claims or are subject to international or regional treaties. Additionally, public opinion and political dynamics can influence the interpretation and enforcement of these clauses, potentially leading to disputes and challenges.

Despite these challenges, stabilization clauses remain a valuable contractual tool for managing regulatory risk in renewable energy projects. In addition, they are a key tool for setting the contractual obligations and justification for adjusting the fiscal provisions according to the R-factor model. In addition, stabilization clauses set the ground for renegotiation clauses, which are another important contracting tool for applying R-factor adjustment.

4.2.2. Renegotiation clauses

Renegotiation clauses are contractual provisions that come into effect when specific events occur, compelling all involved parties to reconvene for negotiations. The purpose of these renegotiations is to readjust the terms of their agreements, aiming to restore the initial balance between the parties. Renegotiation clauses in long-term and capital-intensive projects serve as contractual mechanisms that enable parties to adapt to changing circumstances by adjusting specific terms of the agreement.¹²⁷ These clauses have gained prominence as a response to the dynamic nature of the energy sector (more

¹²⁷ - John Y Gotanda, 'Renegotiation and adaptation clauses in investment contract, revisited' (2003) 36 Vand J Transnat'l L 1461 p.1462

specifically petroleum contracts), where regulatory and market conditions can evolve over time and affect the fiscal regimes of contracts.¹²⁸ This section explores the philosophy and function of renegotiation clauses, their application in adjusting the fiscal regime of renewable energy projects, and the challenges and prospects associated with their implementation.

The philosophy behind renegotiation clauses lies in recognizing that contractual equilibrium can be disrupted when external factors, such as changes in the regulatory fiscal regime, significantly impact the profitability or feasibility of renewable energy projects. These clauses acknowledge the need for flexibility and responsiveness, allowing parties to revisit and modify certain provisions to restore the balance of the contract. By including renegotiation clauses, parties proactively anticipate the possibility of change and create a mechanism to adapt the contractual arrangements accordingly.

Renegotiation clauses in renewable energy projects can primarily find application in adjusting the fiscal regime. Governments often introduce changes to tax laws, subsidies, FITs, or other financial incentives that directly affect the financial viability of renewable energy investments. These changes can impact project returns, investor expectations, and the overall feasibility of the project. Renegotiation clauses provide a means to address these changes by allowing parties to engage in discussions and modify specific contractual terms to restore the economic equilibrium of the project.¹²⁹

¹²⁸ - Zeyad A At Qurashi, 'Renegotiation of international petroleum agreements' (2005) 22 J Int'l Arb 261

¹²⁹ - Iwan Erar Joesoef Rachmani Aprilia Sari, 'Application of Economic Equilibrium Principles in Power Purchase Agreement between PT PLN and Public Private Partnership' (2021) 04 International Journal of Social Science And Human Research 1282 p.1285

Through renegotiation clauses, parties can trigger discussions when significant changes to the fiscal regime occur. These clauses outline the process for assessing the impact of the changes, initiating renegotiation, and establishing parameters for adjusting specific provisions. The renegotiation process allows parties to align the contract with the revised fiscal framework, ensuring that the project remains financially viable and sustainable in light of the new conditions. By enabling open dialogue and collaboration, renegotiation clauses provide a contractual tool to manage the risk of regulatory and legislative changes, promoting the continued development of renewable energy projects.

However, the implementation of renegotiation clauses in renewable energy projects is not without challenges. One key challenge is establishing clear triggers and criteria for initiating the renegotiation process. Defining the threshold for significant changes and ensuring that renegotiation is warranted without unduly limiting governments' ability to enact necessary policy adjustments can be a delicate task. Additionally, the renegotiation process may involve complex negotiations, potentially leading to disputes or delays in reaching a mutually acceptable outcome.

Despite these challenges, renegotiation clauses hold prospects for managing regulatory and legislative risks in renewable energy projects. By providing a contractual framework for adapting to new conditions, they enhance the resilience and sustainability of projects in an evolving regulatory landscape. These clauses offer the potential to overcome obstacles that obstruct and disintegrate renewable energy projects, allowing parties to proactively address changing market conditions and maintain long-term investment security. Through effective implementation renegotiation clauses provide a functioning structure for R-factor mechanism fostering stability, encourage investment, and support the growth of renewable energy initiatives.

Conclusion

Energy is a fundamental human need, and access to affordable and sustainable energy is essential for social and economic development. However, the traditional energy systems have often been characterized by inequalities. To reform and make them just, governments, constantly set new regulations or change them, which only cause imbalance and chaos in the energy systems. That is because the legislators and regulators are always behind the dynamic changes in societies. Justice, as a concept, is dynamic and ever-evolving, reflecting the changing societal norms and values. In the context of the energy sector, justice encompasses not only equitable distribution of resources but also environmental and intergenerational justice. This recognizes the impact of current energy decisions on future generations and emphasizes the need to transition to sustainable energy systems to address climate change and environmental degradation. Therefore, the energy sector faces the challenge of balancing the three dimensions of the energy trilemma: security, affordability, and environmental sustainability. Achieving this balance requires a dynamic and adaptive approach that can respond to changing circumstances and emerging technologies. Flexibility in energy system functions, strategies, plans, and institutions is crucial to maintain this balance without necessitating constant changes in regulations by governments. To address this challenge, in this research, I articulated an energy justice framework based on transactional justice as the complementary, dynamically supportive element of distributional justice that can set energy systems harmonious to the changes across time and different countries.

In this research, I examined the idea of applying the R-factor mechanism and relative supportive contractual tools to adjust fiscal regimes in renewable energy projects, within the framework of transactional energy justice. The research aimed to explore how the proposed mechanism fits into this framework. Since renewable energy projects

involve separate contract settings among various participants (power generator companies, utilities, and governments), a mechanism that fosters dynamic cooperation becomes essential. Recognizing that the fiscal regime forms the core of each energy project and plays a pivotal role in risk management, it is crucial to synchronize fiscal aspects across different contract settings to achieve financial risk management effectively.

The proposed R-factor mechanism offers a dynamic and flexible approach to adjusting fiscal regimes. By assuring investors of a balanced rate of return on their investment and enabling dynamic and flexible reactions to changes in regulations and market prices, the R-factor mechanism instills confidence and stability in the renewable energy sector. It proves particularly crucial for cases where heavy investments in renewable energy projects carry substantial risks. To address diverse project objectives, two different R-factor formulas have been proposed. One formula ensures that incentive rates or energy prices remain competitive with petroleum-based energy, allowing clean energy to effectively compete with fossil fuels without burdening consumers with higher costs. This is instrumental in achieving the energy trilemma's balance, making energy more affordable and secure through the integration of sustainable clean energy. The second formula motivates generator companies to maximize clean energy production by taking more risks, employing advanced technology, and increasing capital investment. This formula applies to cases where renewable energy is used for producing green energy, where competitiveness with fossil fuels is not the primary concern.

As the R-factor mechanism dynamically aligns the trends of each specific renewable energy project with strategies and agendas, it provides a structure for adjusting the fiscal regime that motivates investors to invest while maintaining reasonable and just levels of government support and incentive rates, promoting balance in the energy market.

As the R-factor mechanism is suggested for large and complex renewable energy projects involving participants from different jurisdictions, it raises energy justice concerns that merit further investigation in future research. Nevertheless, the R-factor has demonstrated its effectiveness and fairness in distributing benefits between investors and host states in such projects.

Being a mathematical mechanism, the R-factor offers quantifiable solutions, allowing for measurement and adjustment of its effects on energy justice. The measurements derived can be utilized to enhance energy justice procedures in similar cases in different countries and serve as a reliable source for future decision-making.

Thus, the R-factor aligns with the criteria of the transactional energy justice framework. As a dynamic, flexible, and sustainable mechanism, it promotes balance in the energy system by ensuring fairness in the bargaining and distribution of economic rents in renewable energy projects, ultimately enhancing the energy market. Additionally, the R-factor mechanism is well-suited for international renewable energy investments.

Considering the R-factor mechanism as the core substance of adjusting the fiscal regime within the transactional energy justice framework, the contractual clauses and institutes serve as the necessary form to support its functioning. Several contractual clauses, such as stabilization clauses and renegotiation clauses, have been discussed as essential elements supporting the R-factor mechanism. Moreover, the joint management committee, as a contractual institute, has been explored and concluded to facilitate government supervision effectively without impeding the project's development. It optimizes risk-sharing among participants in the supply chain of contracts within a renewable energy project, creating a structure where different contracts become integrated and respond harmoniously to each other. Consequently, the function of the R-factor is efficiently facilitated.

References

1. Gaines SE and Eriksson A, *Taxation for environmental protection: A multinational legal study* (Greenwood Publishing Group 1991)
2. Gehne K and Brillo R, *Stabilization clauses in international investment law: beyond balancing and fair and equitable treatment* (Institute of Economic Law, Transnational Economic Law Research Center 2017)
3. Harnly NP, *Stranded costs and other economic challenges in electric utility restructuring* (WISE 1998)
4. Jennings D, Feiten J and Bock H, *Petroleum accounting Principles, Procedures and Issues* (5th edn, Professional Development Institute 2000)
5. Roberts P, *Joint Operating Agreements: A Practical Guide* (Globe law and business 2010)
6. Nakhle C, '4 Petroleum fiscal regimes: evolution and challenges' in Daniel P, Keen M and McPherson C (eds), *The taxation of petroleum and minerals* (Routledge 2010)
7. Bhattacharya S and others, 'Hedging strategies for risk reduction through weather derivatives in renewable energy markets' (2015 International Conference on Renewable Energy Research and Applications (ICRERA))
8. Hollmén S, Levihn F and Martinsson G, 'When markets don't deliver : – bilateral hedging by means of PPAs in managing intertemporal price risks in power generation investments' (2022 18th International Conference on the European Energy Market (EEM))
9. Ralston F and others, 'Risk constrained contracting strategies of renewable portfolios' (2010 7th International Conference on the European Energy Market)
10. Tang C and Zhang F, 'Classification, principle and pricing manner of renewable power purchase agreement' (IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science)
11. Bitar E and others, *Optimal contracts for wind power producers in electricity markets* (IEEE 2010)
12. Liu M, Wu FF and Ni Y, *A survey on risk management in electricity markets* (IEEE 2006)
13. Speyer JL, Fan C-H and Banavar RN, *Optimal stochastic estimation with exponential cost criteria* (IEEE 1992)
14. Johnston D, *International Petroleum Fiscal Systems-PSCs* (PennWell Publishing Company 1994)
15. Abdi S and Salarian MA, 'Examining the Contractual Methods and Patterns of Financing Infrastructure Projects with Emphasis on Build, Operation, Transfer Contracts' (2022) 7 International Journal of Finance & Managerial Accounting 115
16. Abdullah MP and others, 'Optimizing time of use (ToU) electricity pricing in regulated market' (2016) 78 Jurnal Teknologi 49
17. Andrews-Speed P, 'Fiscal systems for mining - the case of Brazil' (1998) 13 Minerals & Energy - Raw Materials Report 13
18. Araujo A, 'Marginal Cost & its Variation in Different Economy Scales' (2019) 2 International Journal of Tax Economics and Management 29
19. Attarzadeh M and others, 'Options-based negotiation management of PPP–BOT infrastructure projects' (2017) 35 Construction management and economics 676
20. Auriol E and Picard PM, 'A theory of BOT concession contracts' (2013) 89 Journal of economic behavior & organization 187

21. Bahadoran-Baghbaderani M and Mohamadi A, 'Legal study of foreign investment restrictions and project financing through the implementation of engineering, procurement, construction, and finance (EPCF) contracts' (2021) 27 *Journal encyclopedia of economic law* 29
22. Barbosa L and others, 'Feed-in tariff contract schemes and regulatory uncertainty' (2020) 287 *European Journal of Operational Research* 331
23. Baumol WJ and Sidak JG, 'Stranded costs' (1994) 18 *Harv JL & Pub Pol'y* 835
24. Boroumand RH and others, 'Hedging strategies in energy markets: The case of electricity retailers' (2015) 51 *Energy Economics* 503
25. Bos K and Gupta J, 'Stranded assets and stranded resources: Implications for climate change mitigation and global sustainable development' (2019) 56 *Energy Research & Social Science* 101215
26. Bruck M, Sandborn P and Goudarzi N, 'A Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) model for wind farms that include Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs)' (2018) 122 *Renewable Energy* 131
27. Caldecott B, 'Introduction to special issue: stranded assets and the environment' (2017) 7 *Journal of Sustainable Finance & Investment* 1
28. Cansino JM and others, 'Tax incentives to promote green electricity: An overview of EU-27 countries' (2010) 38 *Energy Policy* 6000
29. Černič JL, 'Corporate human rights obligations under stabilization clauses' (2010) 11 *German Law Journal* 210
30. Chen YQ and others, 'Analysis of project delivery systems in Chinese construction industry with data envelopment analysis (DEA)' (2010) *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management* 598
31. Cottarelli C, 'Fiscal regimes for extractive industries: Design and implementation' (2012) *International Monetary Fund* 67
32. Daintith T, 'Against 'lex petrolea'' (2017) 10 *The Journal of World Energy Law & Business* 1
33. Deng S-J and Oren SS, 'Electricity derivatives and risk management' (2006) 31 *Energy* 940
34. Duncan TE, 'Linear-exponential-quadratic Gaussian control' (2013) 58 *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control* 2910
35. E Tsolas I, 'Benchmarking engineering, procurement and construction (EPC) power plant projects by means of series two-stage DEA' (2020) 1 *electricity* 1
36. Ebrahimi S and Maddahinasab M, 'Controlling Contractor's Rate of Return (ROR) in Risk Service Contracts with R-Factor Mechanism' (2018) 16 *Oil, Gas & Energy Law*
37. Egli F, Steffen B and Schmidt TS, 'A dynamic analysis of financing conditions for renewable energy technologies' (2018) 3 *Nature Energy* 1084
38. Elistratov V and Kudryasheva I, 'Regimes, management and economics of energy complexes on the basis of renewable energy sources for autonomous power supply' (2019) 124 *E3S Web Conf* 04023
39. Friedman LS, 'The importance of marginal cost electricity pricing to the success of greenhouse gas reduction programs' (2011) 39 *Energy Policy* 7347
40. García-Alvarez MT and Mariz-Pérez RM, 'Analysis of the success of feed-in tariff for renewable energy promotion mechanism in the EU: lessons from Germany and Spain' (2012) 65 *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences* 52
41. Gatzert N and Kosub T, 'Risks and risk management of renewable energy projects: The case of onshore and offshore wind parks' (2016) 60 *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 982

42. Gatzert N and Kosub T, 'Determinants of policy risks of renewable energy investments' (2017) 11 *International journal of energy sector management* 28
43. Gotanda JY, 'Renegotiation and adaptation clauses in investment contract, revisited' (2003) 36 *Vand J Transnat'l L* 1461
44. Hall WR, 'Securitization and Stranded Cost Recovery' (1997) 18 *Energy LJ* 363
45. Hazrati M and Heffron RJ, 'Conceptualising restorative justice in the energy transition: changing the perspectives of fossil fuels' (2021) 78 *Energy research & social science* 102115
46. Heffron RJ and McCauley D, 'The concept of energy justice across the disciplines' (2017) 105 *Energy Policy* 658
47. Hosie J, 'Turnkey contracting under the FIDIC Silver Book: What do owners want? What do they get?' (2007) London, UK
48. Hult GTM, Ketchen Jr DJ and Nichols Jr EL, 'An examination of cultural competitiveness and order fulfillment cycle time within supply chains' (2002) 45 *Academy of management Journal* 577
49. Hundt SJJHA, 'Power Purchase Agreements and Financing Renewables: An Interdependency' (2021) 27 *The Journal of Structured Finance* 35
50. Huneke F and others, 'Power purchase agreements: financial model for renewable energies' (2018) *Energy Brainpool White Paper*
51. Jain S, 'Exploring structures of power purchase agreements towards supplying 24x7 variable renewable electricity' (2022) 244 *Energy* 122609
52. Jenkins K and others, 'Energy justice: A conceptual review' (2016) 11 *Energy Research & Social Science* 174
53. Jenkins KE and others, 'Towards impactful energy justice research: transforming the power of academic engagement' (2020) 67 *Energy Research & Social Science* 101510
54. Kamat R and Oren SS, 'Exotic options for interruptible electricity supply contracts' (2002) 50 *Operations Research* 835
55. Karamoozian A and others, 'Risk assessment of renewable energy projects using uncertain information' (2022) 46 *International Journal of Energy Research* 18079
56. Kaschny L, 'Energy Justice and the Principles of Article 194 (1) TFEU Governing EU Energy Policy' (2023) *Transnational Environmental Law* 1
57. Kröger M, Neuhoff K and Richstein JC, 'Contracts for difference support the expansion of renewable energy sources while reducing electricity price risks' (2022) 12 *DIW Weekly Report* 205
58. Kwant KW, 'Renewable energy in The Netherlands: policy and instruments' (2003) 24 *Biomass and Bioenergy* 265
59. Lee CW and Zhong J, 'Financing and risk management of renewable energy projects with a hybrid bond' (2015) 75 *Renewable Energy* 779
60. Lee P, Lam P and Lee WL, 'Risks in energy performance contracting (EPC) projects' (2015) 92 *Energy and Buildings* 116
61. Liu M and Wu FF, 'Risk management in a competitive electricity market' (2007) 29 *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems* 690
62. Loewen J, 'LCOE is an undiscounted metric that inaccurately disfavors renewable energy resources' (2020) 33 *The Electricity Journal* 106769
63. Lund D, 'State participation and taxation in Norwegian petroleum: Lessons for others?' (2014) 3 *Energy Strategy Reviews* 49
64. Luo D and Zhao X, 'Modeling optimal oil production paths under risk service contracts' (2013) 10 *Petroleum Science* 596

65. Maddahinasab M, 'Fiscal analysis of new Iranian petroleum contract called IPC from a legal and contractual perspective' (2017) 15 Oil, Gas & Energy Law
66. Maddahinasab M and others, 'Managing confidential information on petroleum projects in the case of third parties' (2019) Energy Policy Studies
67. Maniruzzaman A, 'Drafting stabilisation clauses in international energy contracts: some pitfalls for the unwary' (2007) 5 Oil, Gas & Energy Law
68. Marinescu N, 'Changes in renewable energy policy and their implications: The case of Romanian producers' (2020) 13 Energies 6493
69. Martin AT, 'Model Contracts: A Survey of the Global Petroleum Industry' (2004) 22 Journal of Energy & Natural Resources Law 281
70. Martinez-Alier J and others, 'Is there a global environmental justice movement?' (2016) 43 The Journal of Peasant Studies 731
71. May N, Neuhoff K and Richstein JC, 'Affordable electricity supply via contracts for difference for renewable energy' (2018) 8 DIW Weekly Report 251
72. Meyer NI, 'European schemes for promoting renewables in liberalised markets' (2003) 31 Energy Policy 665
73. Moon G, 'Arrested ambition? Foreign investor protections, stabilization clauses and fossil-fuelled power generation in developing countries' (2021) 30 Review of European, Comparative & International Environmental Law 313
74. Noilhac A, 'Renewable energy investment cases against Spain and the quest for regulatory consistency' (2020) 71 Questions of International Law 21
75. O'Connor M, Lewis T and Dalton G, 'Operational expenditure costs for wave energy projects and impacts on financial returns' (2013) 50 Renewable Energy 1119
76. Obi M and others, 'Calculation of levelized costs of electricity for various electrical energy storage systems' (2017) 67 Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews 908
77. Oliveira FS, Ruiz C and Conejo AJ, 'Contract design and supply chain coordination in the electricity industry' (2013) 227 European Journal of Operational Research 527
78. Oshionebo E, 'Stabilization clauses in natural resource extraction contracts: legal, economic and social implications for developing countries' (2010) 10 Asper Rev Int'l Bus & Trade L 1
79. Qurashi ZAA, 'Renegotiation of international petroleum agreements' (2005) 22 J Int'l Arb 261
80. Rachmani Aprilia Sari IEJ, 'Application of Economic Equilibrium Principles in Power Purchase Agreement between PT PLN and Public Private Partnership' (2021) 04 International Journal of Social Science And Human Research 1282
81. Schmidt J and others, 'Where the wind blows: Assessing the effect of fixed and premium based feed-in tariffs on the spatial diversification of wind turbines' (2013) 40 Energy Economics 269
82. Shamsi M and Cuffe P, 'Using Binary Prediction Markets as Hedging Instruments: Strategies for Renewable Generators' (2022) 13 IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy 1160
83. Shen W and others, 'A comprehensive review of variable renewable energy levelized cost of electricity' (2020) 133 Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews 110301
84. Shrestha R and Ogunlan S, 'Comparative study of Power Purchase Agreements in the Nepalese environment' (2006) 11 Journal of Financial Management of Property and Construction 133

85. Sovacool BK and Dworkin MH, 'Energy justice: Conceptual insights and practical applications' (2015) 142 *Applied Energy* 435
86. Sovacool BK, Gilbert A and Nugent D, 'An international comparative assessment of construction cost overruns for electricity infrastructure' (2014) 3 *Energy Research & Social Science* 152
87. Taghizadeh-Hesary F and Yoshino N, 'Sustainable solutions for green financing and investment in renewable energy projects' (2020) 13 *Energies* 788
88. Talus K, Looper S and Otilar S, 'Lex Petrolea and the internationalization of petroleum agreements: focus on Host Government Contracts' (2012) 5 *The Journal of World Energy Law & Business* 181
89. Tavafoghi H and Teneketzis D, 'Multidimensional Forward Contracts Under Uncertainty for Electricity Markets' (2017) 4 *IEEE Transactions on Control of Network Systems* 511
90. Tomain JP, 'The past and future of electricity regulation' (2002) 32 *Envtl L* 435
91. Tomic K, 'Stabilization Clauses in Energy Sector' (2020) *Harmonius: J Legal & Soc Stud Se Eur* 258
92. Tran TT and Smith AD, 'Incorporating performance-based global sensitivity and uncertainty analysis into LCOE calculations for emerging renewable energy technologies' (2018) 216 *Applied energy* 157
93. Tsao Y-C, Vu T-L and Lu J-C, 'Pricing, capacity and financing policies for investment of renewable energy generations' (2021) 303 *Applied Energy* 117664
94. Walsh Jr PJ, 'Standstill Agreements: Enterra Validates the Use of Standstill Agreements to Govern Minority Investment Programs' (1985) 42 *Wash & Lee L Rev* 1015
95. Wand R and Leuthold F, 'Feed-in tariffs for photovoltaics: Learning by doing in Germany?' (2011) 88 *Applied Energy* 4387
96. Wenders JT, 'Peak load pricing in the electric utility industry' (1976) *The Bell Journal of Economics* 232
97. Wisner JD and Tan KC, 'Supply chain management and its impact on purchasing' (2000) 36 *Journal of Supply Chain Management* 33
98. Zhang Q and Wang X, 'Hedge contract characterization and risk-constrained electricity procurement' (2009) 24 *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems* 1547
99. Cain C, Lesser J and White B, *A common sense guide to wholesale electric markets*, (2007)
100. Heeter JS, Speer BK and Glick MB, *International best practices for implementing and designing renewable portfolio standard (RPS) policies*, (2019)
101. Jenkins G and Lim H, *An integrated analysis of a power purchase agreement*, (1999)
102. Krecyk CE, Couture TD and Cory KS, *Procurement options for new renewable electricity supply*, (2011)
103. Maddahinasab M, 'Legal and Philosophical Analysis of Ownership and sovereignty over hydrocarbon resources in concern with issues on internationally shared hydrocarbon reservoirs' (University of Zurich 2018)